

Deliverable D6.8

Pilot (ES) Technical report and achieved results (2 | 2)

Deliverable report

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analyzing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
MWD	Measurement-While-Drilling
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/ Quality Control
ROM	Run-of-mine
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
SVM	Support Vector Machine
DEQ	DigiEcoQuarry
WP	Work Package

1 Pilot overview

The Valdilecha quarry is at the forefront of implementing Key Technology Area KTA1, focusing on enhanced extraction, rock mass characterization, and control. The quarry's primary project interest lies in studying and managing fines production from blasting, aiming to increase the yield of high-value final fractions while minimizing lower-value fractions. Various parameters will be measured, including structural rock conditions, lithology changes, geometrical characteristics of blasts, explosive mass, and timing sequence. The quarry will also focus on muckpile characterization, vibrations in the near-field for rock damage evaluation, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for digging. The DigiEcoQuarry approach involves linking KPIs throughout the Mine-to-Mill process to reduce the ratio of unsuitable material for aggregate production, particularly fines.

There have been three exploitation zones:

1. First zone (2021-2023): North of Tradebe's basin 2.
2. Second zone (2021-2025): Southeast area.
3. Third zone (2023-2025): Northwest area.

The Valdilecha quarry has seamlessly incorporated cross-cutting technologies from the project, including Building Information Modelling (BIM), ICT platform, and a cutting-edge IoT/BIM/AI platform. Leveraging the power of artificial intelligence algorithms, these technologies contribute to a comprehensive and integrated approach. BIM facilitates precise modelling of the quarry's structural elements, ICT enhances communication and data transfer efficiency, while the IoT/BIM/AI platform synergistically combines data from various sources for advanced analytics. The implementation of these technologies not only enhances the overall operational efficiency but also positions Valdilecha as a forward-thinking leader in the intersection of mining, technology, and artificial intelligence within the DigiEcoQuarry project.

2 Implemented Technologies and Services

Valdilecha has emerged as a trailblazer in the implementation of the advanced KTA 1 system, aimed at applying techniques for the characterization of the rock mass with the primary goal of refining drilling and blasting operations. This strategic approach seeks to optimize not only the overall efficiency of mining activities but also enhance the accuracy of drilling, a critical aspect for resource maximization and safety in project development. This report closely examines the results achieved in Valdilecha, highlighting also the deploying of cross-cutting technologies for Valdilecha quarry, thereby contributing to ongoing advancement and excellence in the quarry industry.

Secondly, another very challenging KTA 4 frameworks has been implemented for the project and specifically for Valdilecha’s CEMEX quarry involving the process digitalization through ICT solutions, BIM and AI services. In this regard, an outcome of this site is to determine through computer vision if the material being processed meets the expected quality or adjustments have to be made in the extraction and material selection processes, before entering the plant, as well as the automatic grain size determination of both the extracted and processed material, being able to detect oversize material and evaluate grain uniformity, which, in turn, allow to reduce damage in the crushing process and maximize the efficiency of the run-of-mine process.

The present deliverable summarizes the final result of the services implemented in the quarry. Only the activities performed since November 2023 are here reported. Previous work and results were reported in Deliverable D6.2.

2.1 Selection and development of innovative aggregates processing techniques (WP2)

2.1.1 Advanced rock mass characterisation (Task 2.1.)

2.1.1.1 Visual, or optics-based, characterization techniques

2.1.1.1.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Rock mass characterization techniques
Overview	Characterization by applying state-of-the-art techniques namely UAV pre- and post-blast flights, and in-borehole logging using endoscope and Televiwer probes, to identify the lithological and structural rock condition of 23 blasts made in Valdilecha quarry during years 2023 and 2024. The objective of the first set of tools is to build 3D photogrammetric models and map outcropping discontinuities, while the second is to identify lithological and structural features in the walls of the drilled boreholes (see “D2.1-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (I)” and “D2.11-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (II)”). In addition, the endoscope mapping data is integrated with the data monitoring system –logged by the add-on installed in the drill rig– to calibrate the rock mass response to drilling. More information on this technology is provided in Deliverable D2.11 and Technical Report 6 (TR6) “Rock mass characterization in Valdilecha quarry using Measurement-While-Drilling technology”.
Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UAV pre-blast flights to build 3D photogrammetric models and map outcropping discontinuities and obtain the orientation and length of each discontinuity, the spacing between discontinuities, and the areal fracture density P21 (i.e., fracture trace length per unit surface over the investigated area). Borehole logging with a low-cost endoscope camera that it is easy to handle and that allows classifying the rock into seven lithologies and recognize five discontinuity types. Endoscope logging was previously calibrated with an optical televiwer.
Target	Explosive suppliers; software developers; mines and quarries; specialized consultants.

<p>Audience</p>	
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Matrix 300 RTK Universal Edition with a Zenmuse P1 photogrammetric sensor manufactured by DJI (see Figure 1, UPM-M).</p> <p><i>Figure 3 General configuration of the Televiever equipment on the field.</i></p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>UAV flights: To completely survey the highwall face of the blast, the drone is flown manually as close as possible to the face of the block. The camera pitch is also controlled manually to ensure as much as possible its perpendicularity to the face, and the photos are taken manually by the operator. This involves an irregular lateral and forward overlapping between images, resulting in a variable number of images per blast</p>

Televiewer: The setup of the equipment in the field usually takes a minimum of 30 minutes. The time per borehole varies with its length, with an average of about 15 minutes per hole for a borehole length of 15 m at a speed of 1.0 m/min. The logging tool QL40 OBI-2G must be adapted with the proper centralizers. The logging tool is connected to 200 m of 0.125" wireline consisting in a steel armored cable with an insulated conductor at the center that gives power to the tool and allows data exchange with the surface. The wireline is wrapped on the drum of a mini winch that allows hoisting the logging tool through the borehole at a constant velocity. The winch must be connected to a monophasic power source of at least 1100 W. A tripod is placed near the winch to guide the wireline through the blastholes. The winch is connected to the BBox acquisition system USB that works as a link between the logging tool and the computer via the ALT Logger Suite software.

Endoscope: Before the measurements, an in-house-developed plastic centralizer designed by the UPM-M team is fixed to a metallic bar of 1 m attached to the camera and the cable. The measurements were carried out by a single operator who positions the tool on one side of the hole. For each video, the hole ID is annotated in the video, then the recording is started by the operator, and finally, the camera is pushed into the hole until the bottom of the hole. Then recording is stopped, the video is saved, and the operation is repeated in the next hole. A general scheme of this operation and the final processing of the videos is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 (A) PCE-PIC device description. (B) Detail of the plastic centralizer. (C) Field layout of hole logging with the endoscope device. (D) In-hole video analysis.

Communication Protocols -

MAXAM has deployed a local WIFI network composed by a system of permanent antennas that allows connectivity between them outside the pit, and a mobile one that is placed in the working area in line of sight of the fixed antenna. The mobile antenna provides WIFI coverage around it in a range of 400 m, enabling the connection to this local WIFI network of the drone. This allows a Real Time Kinematics (RTK) positioning to correct errors from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). Figure 5 shows images of the onsite installation of the fixed, to the left (internet receptor) and center (Master antenna) and mobile (to the right) antennas.

	<p><i>Figure 5 Images of the antennas system installed: left – WIFI receptor, centre – master antenna, right – mobile antenna.</i></p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>The data captured and generated is stored and managed in internal UPM-M servers considering their large size. The files are processed and analyzed internally with specialized software:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud points about 100 Gb are obtained from the UAV flights, and processed with SMX MultiPhoto module (version 4.4) of the BlastMetrix 3D® software (2023) to build 3D models. The resulting 3D models were analyzed with the JMX Analyst Module (version 4.8) to map discontinuities. • The televiewer files are recorded and processed using the ALT Logger Suite 12.1 and then analyzed by the WellCAD software. • MP4 videos about 50 mb for each hole are obtained from the in-hole logging with the endoscope.
<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>As collateral work not included in the GA, an automatic detection of lithologies from the endoscope videos has been attempted. A script in MATLAB environment has been developed to extract the images of the videos, read the corresponding depths from the digits in the upper left corner and extracts colour properties as red, green, blue pixel intensities and the texture of the images. These data are considered as inputs into a Machine learning model to classify the rock into different classes. The overall accuracy is 92 %, being the best recognition for limestone class. This work has been presented to a high-impact journal (Li et al., 2025) which is currently under review to write this report.</p>
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>The improved knowledge of the rock mass in the block to be blasted allows for a more efficient blast design, boreholes' charging, and control of the muckpile and downstream operations.</p>
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>Automatic lithological and structural identification and classification from the endoscopes videos by using ML techniques tailored for the specific site characteristics.</p>

2.1.1.1.2 Activities performed since November 2023

The UPM-M team monitored ten blasts in the Southeast (SE) and Northwest (NW) working areas of the Valdilecha quarry from February to June 2024 (see Figure 6); blasts are identified in reference to their execution date as B-YYMMDD.

Table 1 details the number of holes and their lengths, logged using low-cost endoscopes. The endoscope manufactured by Forthaus Tech and used in the first campaign of blasts was broken in B-240507 after logging 14 holes. This endoscope did not perform properly in the previous blasts and problems with the memory card prevent monitoring some holes from blast B-240312. Due to the importance of this tool for drilling signals calibration and validation, a new endoscope manufactured by PCE Instruments with similar characteristics than that used previously was purchased by May 2024. It was used to record the in-hole walls of the rest of the blasts.

Table 1 also includes the number of images taken in the preblast flight with a Matrix 300 RTK Universal Edition drone equipped with a Zenmuse P1 photogrammetric sensor from DJI. Due to high wind during the days before blast 230228, no pre-blast flight could be carried out and hence no model of the highwall face for this blast could be built.

No televiewer measurements were executed during this second campaign due to the extensive time required to measure a single hole. The holes logged during the first campaign were used to calibrate the recognition from the endoscope videos. Then, logging is performed only with the endoscope equipment already calibrated.

Figure 6 Blast pit's location at Valdilecha quarry (2nd Campaign).

Table 1 Overview of the manual techniques used in Valdilecha quarry for rock mass assessment (the id of the blasts in each zone is typed with a different color).

Quarry area-Bench	Blast No.	Endoscope ^a		UAV-Flights	
		No. holes / length logged	Fraction of holes of the blast, %	No. images	RTK availability
SE-Bench 2	240209	27 / 345.1 m (F)	96 (tenia 30 holes)	618	Yes
	240228	18 / 228.2 m (F)	75	No flight	No flight
	240322	22 / 233.4 m (F)	91 (25 holes)	450	Yes
	240507	24 / 213.9 m (F, PCEi)	96	737	Yes
	240625	10 / 121.1 m (PCEi)	40 (28 holes)	938	Yes
SE-Bench 3	240604	12 / 164.7 m (PCEi)	80	938	Yes
NW-Bench 1	240312	5 / 64 m (F)	20 (24 holes)	663	Yes
	240404	23 / 285.6 m (F)	88	681	Yes
	240521	29 / 363.2 m (PCEi)	100	626	Yes
	240613	37 / 430.1 m (PCEi)	100	663	No ^b

^aThe endoscope manufacturer is given in brackets

^bThe collar coordinates given by the drill rig are used to correct the coordinates of the pre-blast model by translating the model to the “real” coordinates.

All these data collected has been processed by UPM-M to construct different models on which the following analysis, connected with WP2 tasks, is performed:

- Use of the in-hole logging data to calibrate and validate the classification of the rock condition performed by the processing of the MWD data.
- Drilling QA/QC by analyzing the differences between the planned and drilled hole collar using the model generated from the UAV flights and the georeferencing from the GPS.
- The photogrammetric pre- and post-blast models generated from the UAV flights are also employed to assess the blast design, namely burden of each row and spacing between holes, and to calculate the volume of rock extracted. This analysis aims to correlate the outputs from the blast (i.e., fragmentation and muckpile layout) with downstream parameters.

Detailed information about the application of these techniques can be found in the documents:

- D2.1-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (I)
- D2.11-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (II)
- D2.2- Adaptive blast design and novel explosives, blasting products & systems

2.1.1.2 Use of MWD for rock characterization

2.1.1.2.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Use of Measurement while drilling (MWD) for rock characterization
Overview	MWD data was recorded during two years in Valdilecha quarry from two working campaigns which encompass 17 blasts, 339 boreholes and over 112,000 drilling records. The drilling rig used is a Leopard DI550 Down-the-hole (DTH) modern and automatized unit manufactured by SANDVIK. Each signal obtained from the drilling parameters is processed according to state-of-the-art techniques to remove outliers, filtering the effect of rod addition and removing the influence of hole depth. Correlations and variability among the drilling data are investigated to understand the contribution of each parameter in the drilling process. The processed MWD is calibrated regarding rock conditions using results from the in-borehole logging process to develop an MWD-based rock type classification model.
Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Leopard DI550 DTH unit manufactured by SANDVIK was used to drill the blasts in Valdilecha quarry. The rig is equipped with a TIM3D navigation system and an add-on to monitor MWD parameters. • Two types of files were obtained, first a Drilling Plan Report (DPR) quality file retrieved from the drill rig with a memory stick, and a CAN bus file with MWD records downloaded via Wi-Fi. • A code to processing the MWD signals, calculating derivative features and correlating them with the in-hole logs data. • ML and pattern recognition techniques to classify the input drilling data and to provide rock mass characterization indices.

<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>Explosive suppliers; drilling services suppliers; software developers; mines and quarries; specialized consultants.</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>A drill rig unit with automatic drilling mode and navigation system. In the current case, the rig Leopard DI550 DTH unit manufactured by SANDVIK is equipped with a TIM3D navigation system and an add-on to monitor MWD parameters (see Figure 7).</p> <div data-bbox="612 468 1235 898" data-label="Image"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 7: Sandvik DI550 drill rig at Valdilecha quarry.</i></p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>Driller training and installation of the equipment to enable the drill rig navigation (noticeably a dedicated GPS base station and internet antenna) were done. The importance of the navigation to retrieve the borehole coordinates and incorporate this information to record MWD signals. For each blast, two types of files were obtained: (i) the IREDES quality file that provides among others the hole ID, coordinates of the collar, and starting drilling date and time, while (ii) the CANBUS file from which the three pressures, penetration rate and depth are obtained as function of time. UPM-M has written a MATLAB script to link both files and obtain for each hole the drilling data as function of depth.</p>
<p>Communication Protocols -</p>	<p>GPS, 5G, Wi-Fi, - Data transmission security measures.</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>MWD Data is transmitted to SANDVIK internal servers via Wi-Fi. Then, this is sent to UPM-M by email or uploaded in a specific cloud.</p> <p>Drilling quality data is automatically and real time uploaded to SANDVIK's internal servers (SanRemo), and then downloaded from there by UPM-M. Automatic synchronization of these data in the DEQ data lake was achieved for the last drilling campaigns.</p>
<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>The data structure defined for the application of the ML techniques is depicted in Figure 8. In a first stage, the input data corresponding to the drilling parameters is used to train several ML techniques as Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), targeting the individual recognition of the three geological conditions and the combined criteria assessed. For all the analyses the validation frame corresponds to 10-fold cross validation and division of 20% and 80% of the input data for training and testing, respectively.</p> <p>Furthermore, based on the findings of the initial supervised analysis, one of the classifications using geological criteria is followed to build a final model. To improve the recognition of the classes, the data is resampled to establish a balanced dataset. This new dataset is used to</p>

generate a ML-MWD-based model that predicts with high accuracy different rock categories, using only drilling parameters and derived features.

Figure 8: Flowchart of the classification model used.

<p>Application Features</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic classification of lithological classes using the ML MWD-based model. • Automatic classification of structural classes using a model based in pattern recognition techniques. • The model is constructed for the specific site characteristics. • Includes a MATLAB code with the programming about the initial processing of the signals and 2D-3D visualizations of the classification's outputs.
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p>The training process considers the oversampling of the records for the minority sampled classes. Using a Gaussian SVM algorithm a remarkable prediction accuracy about 98% is obtained for the clay, followed by the disintegrated limestone with 90% accuracy. The other limestones classes are well predicted with accuracies and F1 scores over 80%.</p>
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>Avoiding the use of proprietary black box-type commercial systems; Real time, AI based rock mass description to guide mining and quarrying operations; Site-specific calibration.</p>
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>Following-up of the AI techniques developed in other quarrying or mining operations, with other lithologies and drill rig technologies.</p>

2.1.1.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

During the second campaign, MWD was active in all the blasts. Two blasts (B-240604 and B-240613) could not be used in the analysis as the machine did not record the logging depths during the drilling of these consecutive blasts due to a drill rig network failure issue, so the depth position registered for the MWD records could not be obtained. All efforts were made (and are still being tried at the time of writing this report) to retrieve such depth references. The specification of the data recorded from the blasts in the second campaign is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Drilling data and MWD records per blast for the second blasting campaign in Valdilecha.

Drilling bench ID	No. drilled holes	MWD data available
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		No. holes	No. records	Total length, m
B-240207	25	25	7,870	361.7
B-240228	24	24	7,486	344.4
B-240312	24	21	3,564	289.5
B-240321	22	22	5,393	309.1
B-240404	26	26	8,097	373.9
B-240507	25	25	6,588	333.0
B-240516	28	28	9,802	403.0
B-240604	15	-	-	-
B-240613	37	-	-	-
B-240625	29	28	7,793	369.0

^a Blasts are identified in reference to their execution date as B-YYMMDD.

Blastability assessment has been conducted for the blasts in the second campaign based on the rock lithology and structure identification, using the model and techniques described in the general summary from the previous section (2.1.1.2.1). The objective was to include the identified geological and mechanical characteristics of rocks in the blasting design for each blast. The lithological/structural model constructed using the classification ML-MWD based model to generate explosive’s charging recommendations are depicted in sections 3.1.1 and 3.2.2.

From this analysis, specific indexes based in the strength and alteration levels are derived from MWD parameters, which together with mean MWD parameters are calculated per blast to be consider for fragmentation prediction and muckpile layout analysis (see section 3.1.2).

Detailed information about the application of these techniques can be found in the documents:

- D2.1-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (I)
- D2.11-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (II)
- D2.2-Adaptive blast design and novel explosives, blasting products & systems
- D2.5-Drill-to-mill concept implementation

2.1.2 Novel explosive products that can be adapted to rock conditions: digital systems (Task 2.2.)

2.1.2.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	MAXAM’s innovative explosives characterization and blast design: software & application
Overview	RIOFLEX is an advanced watergel explosive system featuring air-compression sensitization, delivering superior adaptability, precision, and energy control in blasting operations. By integrating innovative blast design methodologies, explosives characterization, and cutting-edge blasting systems, RIOFLEX enhances safety, efficiency, and flexibility beyond traditional emulsions. These advancements leverage enhanced rock mass knowledge and smart blast design tools, including new products and modeling software, to optimize blasting performance. By combining innovative explosive technologies with adaptive design systems, RIOFLEX sets new industry standards for blast optimization, resource efficiency, and operational excellence.

Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced water content for increased energy output • Air-compression sensitization for precise density control • Crosslinker additive for semi-solid stability • Adjustable energy and density parameters according to the rock properties and geometrical conditions of the blast • Compatibility with different ammonium nitrate blendings using the same matrix and unit for customization
Target Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mining companies • Quarry operators • Construction and infrastructure projects • Drilling and blasting contractors
Hardware Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pumping and loading unit (MMU-Mobile Manufacturer Unit) with density control • Real-time monitoring sensors • Digital interface for on-site adjustments • Compatibility with blast design software
Installation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No permanent installation is required. MMUs travels during the day to the quarry and leave after finishing charging. • Simple integration with existing blast design software • User-friendly system allowing seamless adoption by blasting teams
Communication Protocols -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wireless data transfer or USB data transfer • Integration with digital blasting platforms
Data Storage & Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud-based storage for blast performance records • Secure and encrypted data handling
AI Integration & Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart sensors for real-time density and energy adjustments • Automated feedback loops for precision blasting
Application Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instantaneous density and energy adjustments • Enhanced control over stemming length and explosive migration • Selective loading and precision blasting techniques • Possibility to vary matrix/ AN Blending % with the same unit and product
Security & Compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meets international safety and environmental standards • Compliance with regulatory frameworks for explosive handling • Built-in security features to prevent unauthorized access
Performance Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved fragmentation efficiency • Reduction in blast-induced damage and vibrations • Higher energy output per kilogram • Reduced operational delays due to real-time adjustments
Support &	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular unit calibration

Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-site training for optimal usage
Business Model & Pricing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible pricing model based on usage and scale • Customizable packages for different mining operations
Competitive Advantage	<p>The RIOFLEX system offers a unique product in the market, featuring an air-compression sensitization mechanism that provides significant operational advantages. This technology allows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Precise loading and stemming control by pumping at the final density, eliminating waiting times. Instantaneous density and energy variation within the borehole, enabling real-time adjustments based on rock characteristics and blast geometry. <p>Additionally, RIOFLEX incorporates a crosslinker additive that transforms the product into a semi-solid state within 10-20 seconds, preventing explosive migration through rock fractures. Unlike traditional emulsions, RIOFLEX is a watergel, allowing for lower water content in its formulation and a higher-density matrix, which enhances energy output per kilogram. Furthermore, with a single unit, it can either function as a 100% matrix-based explosive or be blended with ammonium nitrate-based formulations, offering flexibility to adapt to varying rock conditions.</p>
Future Enhancements	<p>To further enhance RIOFLEX's performance and adaptability, several advancements are being explored:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advanced Sensitization Control – Incorporating smart sensors and automated feedback systems to dynamically adjust explosive density and energy in real-time based on in-hole conditions. - Eco-Friendly Formulations – Reducing environmental impact by optimizing the watergel composition to include biodegradable additives and green AN and even exploring alternative oxidizers to lower emissions. - Integration with Digital Blasting Platforms – Expanding compatibility with AI-driven blast design software and digital monitoring tools to improve precision, data logging, and performance analytics. - Fully Automated Robotic Loading Systems – The integration of robotic units with autonomous navigation and AI-driven control systems will enable a fully automated explosive loading process.

2.1.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

No specific blasts different than those required to meet the production figures of the quarry were carried out during the project. This means that no changes in the drilling grid used by CEMEX were implemented. Blastholes position was defined in situ with a measuring tape by the drill rig operator according to the nominal drilling grid used in the quarry, i.e., burden in the range of 5.5 m and spacing between holes of 7 m. The holes of the first row were marked with respect to the crest and subsequent rows were defined from the previous ones. This will lead to uncontrolled variations in the burden of the first row within and between blasts. No other changes than those caused by this working procedure occurred during the tests, where the changes implemented were in the navigation mode of the drilling rig, explosive type and delay (detonators types and sequence). Table 3 describes the general characteristics of the blasts monitored during the second campaign of the project. From the 10 blasts analyzed, 5 were used as baseline with the common explosive and non-electric detonators and 11 were performed with RIOFLEX and electronic detonators. "Blast Type" column indicate the baseline (BL) or new product (NP) blasts.

Table 3 General characteristics of the blasts in the second campaign: location, drilling and layout

Blast ID	Blast ref	Blast Type	Location		Drill rig		Layout			
			Pit	Bench	Rig	Drill plan navigation	Main face DD/Dip, °	Lateral Face	No. rows	No. holes
240209	16	BL	SE	2	LDI550	Imported	5/24	Yes	2	30
240228	17	BL	SE	2	LDI550	Imported	NM ^a	No	2	24
240312	18	BL	NW	1	LDI550/L6	Imported	97/20	No	3	24
240322	19	BL	SE	2	LDI550	Imported	9/19	No	2	25
240404	20	NP	NW	1	LDI550	Imported	99/22	No	3	26
240507	21	NP	SE	2	LDI550	Imported	3/19	No	2	25
240521	22	NP	NW	1	LDI550	Imported	104/17	No	3	29
240604	23	NP	SE	3	LDI550	Imported	20/20	No	2	15
240613	24	NP	NW	1	LDI550	Imported	98/19	Yes	3	37
240625	25	BL	SE	2	LDI550	Imported	99/14	Yes	2	28

^a No measurement (NM): The pre-blast flight could not be made due to excessive wind

During the second campaign, explosive density was adapted to rock characterization obtained from MWD system as explained in:

- D2.1-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (I)
- D2.11-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (II)
- D2.2-Adaptive blast design and novel explosives, blasting products & systems
- D2.5-Drill-to-mill concept implementation

2.1.3 Technologies for explosive characterization: energy and detonation pressure

2.1.3.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Detonation velocity and pressure measurements
Overview	<p>The detonation pressure of ANFO and RIOFLEX has been determined utilizing pressure gauges based on low-carbon resistor (LCR) technology, as detailed in deliverable D2.3, to include somehow the effect of the explosive in the vibration prediction model. These gauges have been manufactured by the UPM-M team.</p> <p>Detonation velocity was recorded using a probe cable whose linear resistance is known (10.8 Ω/m). In this case, the cable is connected to one of the channels of the acquisition unit (next to the assigned to vibration recording).</p>
Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LCR-based gauges were employed together with the detonation velocity probe cable, which is the first time in history (in authors' knowledge) in performing this dual measurement. • A data acquisition system consisted of a junction between the DATATRAP II and a USB oscilloscope connected to a laptop using a sampling rate of 125 MHz (sampling period of 8 ns). • A probe cable connected to the channels of the acquisition unit for detonation velocity measurements.
Target	Mining and quarrying operations; explosive suppliers

Audience	
<p style="text-align: center;">Hardware Requirements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LCR-based gauges (see Figure 9). <p style="text-align: center;">Figure 10: Connection scheme of the pressure gauges. From: (Gómez, 2024).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A probe cable connected to the channels of the acquisition unit for detonation velocity measurements.
<p style="text-align: center;">Installation Process</p>	<p>Detonation pressure: The gauges were axially placed approximately 5 m from the collar of the monitored blasthole. The connection system from the pressure gauge to the power supply was made via a BNC to an RCA jack adaptor. Then, the power supply is connected to the data acquisition system, which consisted of a junction between the DATATRAP II and a USB oscilloscope connected to a laptop. The power supply and the laptop used were put inside a rugged box to prevent any damage to the system.</p> <p>Detonation velocity: After insert the sensors inside the hole, connect the probe cable to one of the channels of the acquisition unit (next to the assigned to vibration recording).</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>LCR-based gauges were employed together with the detonation velocity probe cable, which is the first time in history (in authors' knowledge) in performing this dual measurement.</p>

2.1.4 Digitalization of blast design and blast results (Task 2.3.)

2.1.4.1 Advanced techniques for blast design

2.1.4.1.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Digital 3D model of the blast
Overview	<p>A digital 3D model is constructed to represent the geometrical characteristics of the bench to be blasted with high accuracy. The inputs of the model correspond to cloud points from the UAV flights, and for the boreholes the collar position (coordinates) obtained from drill rig navigation, and their hole path using a surveying probe. Relevant information to analyze blast design and geometry could be retrieved from these models as drilling scheme or blasted rock volume. In addition, the information from the explosive mass is provided in a file for each MMUs after the charging operation, which combined with the volume allows to derive the powder factor.</p>
Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initial measurements with the drone and the hole surveying probe are necessary after the drilling operation and previous to the blast. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data is processed using Agisoft MetaShape Professional version 2.1.1 (2024) to build the cloud point, then it is trimmed and under sampled with CloudCompare (2017). Then, MATLAB routines are created to process the point cloud, build a triangulated surface, and incorporate the hole path coordinates according to the specific characteristics of the operation and the format of the files. • A 3D model (see Figure 11) is generated to calculate burden between holes and five different procedures are proposed for the calculation of the volume of rock that is blasted. <div data-bbox="491 1070 1350 1574" data-label="Figure"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 11: Blasthole profiles for burden calculation at different depths in blast 230120.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The information from the explosive mass is used to calculate the powder factor in reference to the blasted volume calculated.
Target Audience	Mining and quarrying operations; explosive suppliers; mine and quarry subcontractors.
Hardware Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Matrix 300 RTK Universal Edition with a Zenmuse P1 photogrammetric sensor manufactured by DJI.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pulsar Micro Probe Mk3 (HDP) to measure in each borehole a set of azimuths and dips at lengths steps of 1 m (see Figure 12). <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 12: Pulsar Micro Probe Mk3 operation.</i></p>
Installation Process	No permanent installation is required. Both measurements, with the drone and the surveying probe, are executed after drilling operation and previous to the charging operation for each blast.
Communication Protocols	A mobile antenna provides WIFI coverage around it in a range of 400 m, enabling the connection to this local WIFI network of the drone. This allows a Real Time Kinematics (RTK) positioning to correct errors from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS).
Data Storage & Management	<p>The data captured and generated is stored and managed in internal UPM-M servers. The files are processed and analyzed internally with specialized software:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud points (about 100 GB size for each block) are obtained from the UAV flights, and processed with SMX MultiPhoto module (version 4.4) of the BlastMetrix 3D® software (2023) to build 3D models. A MATLAB script reads the file generated by the hole survey probe (text file) and enables for visualization of the distribution of the azimuth and dip of the holes.
Competitive Advantage	The model represents the real and accurate geometrical conditions of the bench and the drilled holes, providing significant information for the decision-making process during the blast design and the charging operation.
Future Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the availability of the RTK system to obtain accurate images from the UAV flights. Incorporate data from MWD to guide charging considering geometrical aspects and rock properties.

Section	Description
Service Name	Blast design digital tools (X-Blast, MAXAM Blast Center, X-Truck Logger)
Overview	A suite of digital solutions designed to enhance blast design, execution, and analysis through real-time data synchronization, AI-driven insights, and cloud-based management. These tools integrate advanced simulation, monitoring, and optimization functionalities to improve safety, efficiency, and precision in blasting operations.

Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - X-Blast (3D blast design and simulation software) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MAXAM Blast Center (Cloud-based management and real-time analysis platform) - X-Truck Logger (Digital twin system for real-time borehole measurement and explosive loading optimization)
Target Audience	Mining engineers, blasters, quarry operators, and blasting service providers seeking to optimize design, execution, and compliance with regulatory standards.
Hardware Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - X-Blast: High-performance PC with GPU acceleration for 3D rendering. - Blast Center: Cloud-based, accessible via web browser. - X-Truck Logger: Rugged portable device with integration capabilities for X-Truck's PLC.
Installation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - X-Blast: Software installation on local machines. - Blast Center: Web-based platform, no local installation required. - X-Truck Logger: Pre-installed on the device, requires connection to the X-Truck system.
Communication Protocols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wireless data synchronization via cloud services. - XML file export for seamless integration with electronic initiation systems. - Real-time data transfer between X-Truck Logger and X-Truck PLC.
Data Storage & Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cloud-based data storage via MAXAM Blast Center. - Real-time synchronization of blast designs, execution parameters, and performance data. - Traceability of design changes for compliance and audit purposes.
AI Integration & Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-driven optimization of blast parameters based on rock properties and real-time field data. - Automated recalculation of explosive loading based on borehole deviations. - AI-powered risk assessment for flyrock, vibration, and damage estimation.
Application Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3D blast design and real-time simulation. - Borehole measurement and recalculation of charge distribution. - Electronic initiation sequencing and vibration analysis. - Cloud-based collaboration for real-time blast adjustments. - Digital twin technology for remote monitoring and optimization.
Security & Compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Secure cloud storage with encrypted data transmission. - Full traceability of all design modifications. - Compliance with environmental and safety regulations for vibration control and flyrock management.
Performance Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accuracy of blast execution vs. design. - Reduction in vibration levels and flyrock incidents. - Optimization of fragmentation size distribution. - Improvement in loading efficiency and reduction in explosive waste.
Support & Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical support via MAXAM. - Regular software updates with new features. - On-site and remote training for users.
Business Model & Pricing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subscription-based model for MAXAM Blast Center. - License-based pricing for X-Blast software. - Hardware and software bundle pricing for X-Truck Logger.
Competitive Advantage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End-to-end digital integration from design to execution. - AI-powered optimization and predictive analytics. - Real-time cloud synchronization for improved collaboration. - Seamless compatibility with MAXAM's blasting ecosystem.

Future Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expanded AI capabilities for automated blast parameter optimization. - Enhanced machine learning models for predictive fragmentation analysis. - Increased integration with autonomous drilling and loading systems.
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2.1.4.2 Blast output control: fragmentation, rock damage, muckpile properties

2.1.4.2.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Digital 3D models from UAV flights to assess blast output control
Overview	<p>Post-blast flights over the blasting areas were conducted with the Matrix 300 RTK drone to assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The fragmentation of the material in the surface of the muckpile from the analysis of the resulting 3D models. • The effect of blasting on the muckpile layout by calculating profiles or sections of the pre- and post-blast triangulated surfaces from each of the holes of the last row in the direction of the rock motion. • Analysis of backbreak focusing on a methodology involving 3D modelling, fracture marking, and data processing in MATLAB.
Key Components	Pre- and post-blast UAV flights
Target Audience	Mining and quarrying operations; explosive suppliers; blasting subcontractors.
Hardware Requirements	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Matrix 300 RTK Universal Edition with a Zenmuse P1 photogrammetric sensor manufactured by DJI.
Installation Process	The process begins with the acquisition of data through drone flights over the blasting site. High-resolution images are collected to create accurate 3D models of the blast area. To survey completely the post-blast block, the drone flight is carried out automatically as close as possible to the block.
Communication Protocols	A mobile antenna provides WIFI coverage around it in a range of 400 m, enabling the connection to this local WIFI network of the drone. This allows a Real Time Kinematics (RTK) positioning to correct errors from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS).
Data Storage & Management	<p>The data captured and generated is stored and managed in internal UPM-M servers (large size of the files should be considered). The files are processed and analyzed internally with specialized software SMX MultiPhoto (version 4.4) of the BlastMetrix 3D® software (2023) to build 3D models.</p> <p>Fragmenter software to perform an automatic fragmentation analysis of the muckpile layout.</p>
Competitive Advantage	New tools to assess blasting outputs such as fragmentation and muckpile layout and properties, resulting in: (i) operational optimization and digital traceability; (ii) more sustainable, efficient and safer resources exploitation.
Future	Improving the availability of the RTK system to obtain accurate images from the UAV flights.

Enhancements	
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2.1.4.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

A Drone Matrix 300 RTK Universal Edition was used to survey the muckpiles from 10 blasts carried out in Valdilecha in 2024. Fragmenter module, version 4.9.3 (3GSM, 2024), is used to obtain the size distribution from the 3D models of the muckpiles. More information on the procedure followed can be found in the technical report TR3a included in Appendix D of deliverable D2.2.

Table 4 shows the characteristics of the post-blast flights made in the second campaign. The distance between the center of two adjacent pixels or ground sample distance (GSD) is the driving parameter for the degree of details a 3D shows. This parameter depends, among others, on the flight characteristics summarized Table 4. The lower detection limit of the analysis is given at three times of the GSD (3GSM, 2024), and all particles smaller than the detection limit are generically called “fines”. This means that the way of image taking and processing is tied to the level of detail that the algorithm can resolve.

Table 4 Characteristics of post-blast flights and resolution of the muckpiles models for blasts of the second campaign

Blast id.	240209	240228	240312	240322	240404	240507	240521	240604	240613	240625
No. images	190	273	588	464	378	500	410	541	666	391
Flight height, m	50	40	55	50	65	40	60	40	55	50
Endlap × Sidelap, %	80×80	80×80	80×80	85×80	80×80	80×80	80×80	80×80	80×80	80×80
GSD, mm	5.71	4.58	3.12	5.50	4.23	5.01	4.06	6.27	3.53	5.91
MPS, mm	26.50	19.63	10.72	22.05	12.52	22.31	12.04	11.10	14.47	16.61

Using the Fragmenter software an automatic fragmentation analysis is performed on the muckpile models, which takes between 30 and 50 minutes depending on the size of the Region of Interest (ROI). From this analysis, 23 fragmentation models providing size distributions are obtained, to further be correlated with the plant KPIS (see section 2.1.5). The muckpile profile have been predicted for 5 blasts; more detail on this results are included in section 3.1.3.

2.1.5 Integration of TTS and plant monitoring systems to assess downstream parameters per blast: mass hauled and plant KPIS (T2.4/T6.2)

2.1.5.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Drill to mill integration
Overview	The Drill-to-Mill methodology exemplifies the value of integrating diverse datasets across the quarry cycle. Key data streams, including MWD data, explosive performance metrics, fragmentation analyses, digging rates, and comminution energy consumption, have been systematically combined and analyzed. Each partner contributed unique expertise to ensure comprehensive data coverage and actionable insights.

<p>Key Components</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MWD and Rock Mass Data: Provided by Sandvik’s drilling equipment and analyzed by UPM-M and MAXAM. • Explosive Performance Metrics: Recorded and evaluated collaboratively by MAXAM and UPM-M. • Fragmentation Analysis: Captured and interpreted using UPM’s tools and methodologies. • Digging and hauling activities: CEMEX records in an EXCEL file with the number of trips made daily by each truck to the dumping points for each month. The truck tracking system (TTS) is monitored five out of six trucks used to haul the material in the quarry and the two excavators; ABAUT download the data and share it by a .csv file. • Plant KPIs: Documented by CEMEX and analyzed by UPM-M for downstream effects.
<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>Mining and quarrying operations</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conveyor belt scales in the plant • Tracking sensors on trucks and excavators • Drill rig with MWD system • UAV
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>The data captured and generated is stored and managed in internal UPM-M servers (large size of the files should be considered). The files are processed and analyzed internally with specialized software SMX MultiPhoto (version 4.4) of the BlastMetrix 3D® software (2023) to build 3D models.</p> <p>‘Fragmenter’ software to perform an automatic fragmentation analysis of the muckpile layout</p> <p>For the TTS, ABAUT provided via email a .csv file with 32 fields associated to each complete loading and hauling cycle starting from the loading position and ending at the unloading destination.</p> <p>Downstream parameters monitored in a daily basis in the plant are provided by CEMEX.</p>
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>Seamless traceability of material from source to destination, a critical capability in operations where material from multiple blasts is processed simultaneously.</p> <p>The MATLAB-based analysis methodology further enhances this advantage by accurately allocating plant KPIs to specific blasts based on material contribution ratios, creating a closed-loop optimization system.</p>
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>Installing loading cell units on trucks and excavators to eliminate the reliance on nominal payload calculations, this could significantly improve mass measurement accuracy.</p> <p>Transitioning from daily plant measurements to real-time monitoring would allow for more responsive adjustments to processing parameters.</p> <p>Integration of machine learning algorithms with predictive models that automatically suggest optimal blast parameters based on historical performance data, further reducing variability and improving downstream processing efficiency.</p>

2.1.5.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Table 5 shows the plant KPIs of each blast for the second campaign. They are calculated from the weighted means of the basic plant parameters for the days in which each blast is loaded; two weights $W1=R_{Bi}^2$ and $W2=R_{Bi}^3$ are used. The number of available days and the mean and standard deviation of the R index are also given; they describe the homogeneity of the sources of the plant feed. A similar degree of blending is made in both campaigns, and the mean R_{Bi} is 0.77 and 0.80, respectively.

Table 5 Plant KPIs per blast for the second campaign.

Blast	No. days	R _{Bi}		Weights W1=R _{Bi} ²						Weights W2=R _{Bi} ³					
		Av	Std	P90b, %	FPsk, %	FRej, %	TPL %	TCDD min/t	WPL kWh/t	P90b, %	FPsk, %	FRej, %	TPL %	TCDD min/t	WPL kWh/t
240209	11	0.87	0.28	44.0	42.9	53.6	91.7	0.000	0.58	43.9	43.0	53.5	91.8	0.000	0.59
240228	10	0.72	0.37	42.3	35.5	59.7	90.6	0.000	0.51	42.1	35.4	59.8	90.6	0.000	0.50
240312	6	0.62	0.32	45.8	38.3	56.7	91.7	0.000	0.49	46.3	38.1	56.9	92.5	0.000	0.50
240322	9	0.70	0.34	38.8	36.5	58.9	82.9	0.000	0.66	38.7	36.4	58.9	82.2	0.000	0.68
240404	5	0.89	0.14	41.9	41.6	54.1	83.2	0.085	0.41	41.9	41.7	54.0	83.5	0.083	0.41
240507	7	0.85	0.23	41.7	35.0	60.0	93.9	0.000	0.47	41.8	35.0	60.0	94.1	0.000	0.47
240521	7	0.81	0.29	44.1	32.7	62.3	92.0	0.107	0.41	44.2	32.7	62.3	92.3	0.108	0.40
240604	7	0.76	0.31	40.7	34.6	60.4	90.0	0.000	0.40	40.7	34.8	60.2	89.6	0.000	0.40
240613	9	0.87	0.19	47.9	31.8	63.2	83.5	0.241	0.28	48.0	31.7	63.3	83.1	0.246	0.29
240626	6	0.90	0.14	34.9	34.1	61.5	92.2	0.145	0.33	34.6	34.2	61.4	92.1	0.143	0.33

^a Green and light green are blasts in benches 2 and 3 of SE pit, respectively; grey are blasts in bench 1 of the NW pit.

^b Also identified as P_{90}^*

2.2 Identification of data inputs from cyber & physical quarrying system and development of sensors, automation and process control (WP3)

2.2.1 Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery (Task 3.3.)

2.2.1.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	MEMT [Mobile Equipment Monitoring Tool]
Overview	The development of MEMT is based on the state of improving the productivity and the performance of the mining equipment. The solution, based on self-developed, OEM independent hardware and ML – AI reporting system helps to capture, analyze & report different mobile machinery KPIs.
Key Components	Hardware: Self-develop plug and play sensor unit mounted in any type of machinery Software: AI-ML reporting system able to monitor & report performance and production KPIs
Target Audience	Industry: Mining & construction industry. Main targets: Mine managers, mining experts, continuous performance managers and mining companies in general in need of a digital solution for monitoring the machinery performance

Hardware Requirements	about Edge sensor unit & internet connection
Installation Process	Plug and play solution that can be installed in 10min in the mobile machinery without the need of accessing the CanBUS of the mobile machinery or without the need of any retrofit kit. The Edge device can be installed at any position in the cabin of the mobile equipment. It contains an antenna that needs to be orientated to the sky. The sensor unit can be connected to the electrical supply via a 12/24V socket in the cabin or to any other power source.
Communication Protocols -	Data transmission based on terrestrial communication [2G – 3G – 4G – 5G]
Data Storage & Management	The data, once collected by the sensor unit, is transmitted to the servers of about via TC. Once received, the data is stored, processed and integrated in the reporting system. All the data is stored in our cloud system and secure via compliance considerations and backups.
AI Integration & Implementation	AI models based on, machine learning, deep learning, neuronal networks and AI algorithms that detect automatically the different machinery activities. The different activities are integrated in the reporting system according to the different KPIs to report.
Application Features	User interface with access to the reporting system. The different modules of the reporting system are: Production and productivity Fleet efficiency Mine organization & Machinery availability Idle times & inefficiencies Communication and reporting
Security & Compliance	Compliance with European standards in a matter of GDPR. Hardware protected against accessing and Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data.
Performance Metrics	Time to login to the platform Access and refresh of the dashboard Update ratio of the platform Integration of the KPIs
Support & Maintenance	Technical support, training and assistance. Also, integration of monitoring KPIs at different reporting systems. Sales, up selling and marketing activities for commercialization.
Business Model & Pricing	SaaS model with the possibility of paying-as-you-go based on different scalable and integrated modular products. Each module has its price and all the modules can be integrated or purchased as standalone features or being combined for having the full monitoring system capabilities
Competitive Advantage	The unique and modular system of about is completely OEM independent. In addition, it is a plug & solution that can be installed without the necessity of sending the machine to the workshop. The installation could be done in 10 minutes by the local team and is CanBus independent. In addition, for accessing the platform there is no special need or requirement just a normal internet connection.

<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>Integration of the camera system for detecting different activities</p> <p>Enhancement of the AI algorithms</p> <p>Integration of new KPIs</p> <p>Enhancement of the reporting system</p>
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2.2.1.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Since Q4 2023, about has integrated a new dashboard system. This dashboard system has been integrated after contacting the pilot site and making it according to their operational needs.

In addition, the expert system has been enhanced for integrating the different transport routes and it's more relevant KPIs related to production, machinery and distances [see figure below]

Figure 13 Transports routes KPIs

Also, following the different KPIs from other WP, it has been included the different durations of the loading, unloading and idling activities. This new dashboard, see Figure 14, helps to understand the possible bottlenecks during the activities mentioned before and its possible improvements.

Figure 14 Cycle and Loading times

2.3 Development of an integrated IoT/BIM/AI platform for smart quarrying (WP4)

2.3.1 ICT platform design and implementation (Task 4.2)

The ICT platform in fact is not specific to a given quarry. In D4.2, titled “Report on IQS Design and Architecture,” the design and architecture of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), developed by AKKODIS, are described. The implementation of this architecture and site’s specific development were described in D4.6 “Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment”. Hence, more details could be found as follow:

- The IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site, are described in section 3.1 of D4.3.
- The Centralized data management platform and the CDMP front-end are described in section 3.2 of D4.3.
- Transport service, Plant production service, Environmental data management service, Health and safety service are described in section 3.2.3 of D4.6
- Business management tools Section 3.4 of D4.6
- The data lake, the databases, the IoT platform and Talend integration are described respectively in section 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6 and 3.2.7 of D4.6
- The data connectors are described in section 3.3 of D4.6

The following 3 figures show the front-end welcome Home page, the Shared data screen and the plant production screen created for CEMEX.

Figure 15 CDMP Front-End: Welcome page – “Home” screen.

Figure 16 CDMP Front-End – “Shared Data” screen.

Figure 17 CDMP Front-End – “Plant production” screen.

In CEMEX, several quarry processes (Production, Transport, Environment, Drilling) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format.

The data integration process has been implemented. Data are flowing at various frequencies (daily, monthly) depending on the use case. Data integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern adopted by Abaut and Roctim to push data from Abaut analytics system and Roctim/PlantSmith systems to the IQS and to pull data from the IQS by the data consumers. The final result of the IQS data integration within the project across all sites including the data availability status in the data lake is described in section 4 of D4.6.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring. The dashboards are described in section 4.3 of D4.2 and in section 3 of D4.6.

All the dashboards created for CEMEX are accessible in one power-bi application accessible to pilot site’s users as shown in next figure.

Figure 18 DEQ Power BI Application for CEMEX

2.3.2 Data warehouse and AI Services(Task 4.3.)

The Data Warehouse was designed by SIGMA and is reported in D4.4 “Report on the Architecture of the Data Warehouse and its Integration”. The Data Warehouse was designed in the framework of the IQS global system that seats in the cloud. It is not specifically designed for this pilot. Nevertheless, it encompasses the functionality of storing and processing data to represent the results of the services implemented for CEMEX-Valdilecha also.

The AI services designed in the project are summarised in the following table mentioning the pilot quarry they belong to:

Table 6 AI Services developed for the different pilots.

AI Service Area	Pilot site	SIGMA	UPM-AI
Hawkeye (CV) COLORIMETRY (QUAL)	CEMEX	X	X
Hawkeye (CV) GRAIN SIZE	CEMEX	X	X
Stock Forecast (CV) STOCKPILE VOLUME	Holcim & Vicat	X	X
Predictive Maintenance (PrMa) - ANOMALIES DETECTION (Acoustic&video&...)	CSI	X	X
Metaquarry (Document Mgt)	Holcim & Vicat	X	
Consumptions & production forecast	CIMPOR	X	X

In this deliverable only the ones pertaining to Cemex Valdilecha’s quarry are described.

It is important to mention that in the deliverable D4.3 “Report on the AI Algorithms and Services”, detailed design specifications can be found and the contents that can be found here are in some cases a summary of the text in the deliverable.

The first service aims at estimating the composition of aggregates inline production using visual inputs captured by cameras. This service is being implemented in CEMEX-Valdilecha in which limestones are being extracted as aggregates. Together with this material, clays appear, which represent non-profitable waste, and which is desired to minimize or, at least, differentiate to optimize the processes in the treatment plant.

In addition, one of the key factors in classifying the final product of aggregates is the size of the particles that make up the material, as the size of the particles in aggregates plays a crucial role in determining their suitability for different applications. In this regard, the aim of the second AI service implemented in CEMEX-Valdilecha is to automate the process of determining whether the treated material meets technical specifications. By analyzing the screening efficiency, it can quickly identify any issues with the screening process. This allows for timely repairs or replacements of screens, ensuring the proper functioning of material treatment processes.

Therefore, in the case of the CEMEX-Valdilecha Pilot, two AI services have been designed specifically. The two services are centered on the analysis of the quality of the material. Firstly, in the primary section of the plant that is analysing images from 2 cameras installed at the primary crusher and at a conveyor belt which is used to carry the material that is rejected at the roller screen of the latter crusher. In this way all the material that enters the plant is supervised by Computer Vision algorithms that **process the colour of the material** together with the shape and texture determines if the material being processed is of the expected quality or adjustments have to be made in the extraction and material selection processes, before entering the plant. In addition, another outcome of this service is the automatic determination the size of the rock fragments in order to detect oversize material, which, in turn, allows to reduce damage in the crushing process.

Secondly, at the secondary section of the plant, another camera has been installed at a conveyor belt that is used to transport the produced 4-20 mm material to its stockpile from the specific material silo. In this case a **granulometry service** is supervising that the size of the aggregates produced is what is expected.

2.3.2.1 Artificial Intelligence implemented services

2.3.2.1.1 Quality Determination Service (Colorimetry)

2.3.2.1.1.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	QUALITY DETERMINATION SERVICE
Overview	<p>This service aims at estimating the quality of aggregates (composition) inline production using visual inputs captured by cameras. The system will be non-intrusive and will allow for maximizing the run of the mining process by improving site planning and controlling the grinding process. It will also support automated notifications and keep a historical record to further analyze the data. The information will be collected and processed while keeping the mine in production, fostering direct actions on the operations.</p> <p>In the Valdilecha pilot site, limestones are being extracted as aggregates. Together with this material, muds appear, which represent non-profitable waste and which is desired to minimize or, at least, differentiate to optimize the processes in the treatment plant. Therefore, this service will provide the aggregate classification on-line based on artificial intelligence and image processing technology analyzing this mixed material that enters the quarry. At the end two cameras are used, one at the primary crusher and one at the conveyor belt that captures all material selected/discarded by the roller screen at the crusher. In the diagram below the camera positioning is outlined (orange numbering).</p> <p>Figure 19 Valdilecha's primary schematic configuration and camera positioning.</p>
Key Components	A general Architecture diagram is appended:

Figure 20 Component architecture

It is important to highlight that the components span from local components to components basically residing at cloud infrastructures. In the quarry cameras are used to record images from the primary processes at the plant (crusher and conveyor belt) that give the capacity to the CV system to analyze the quality of all the material entering the plant. The conveyor belt used is the one that transports all the material that has been initially discarded from the primary crusher roller screen. To control the cameras, the local installation uses an industrial server that feeds these cameras and allows for a first image processing stage. The latter also holds a communication controller that uses a 4G SIM modem to transmit via an IOT network the filtered images to the SIGMA components that run the AI models used to detect the color, size and segments contained on the images able to determine them material basic composition centered on limestone and clay. The latter composition helps the quarry manager to determine how good and reliable is the material extraction process on the quarry's exploitation front. Additionally, alarms are generated depending on the occupation level at the primary crusher roller sieve and also when bigger rocks than a programmable threshold are detected at the crusher entrance. To avoid possible accidents or damages on the jaw crusher.

The AI processed information data is sent securely to the IQS datalake and later on to the Datawarehouse where the data is properly organized to facilitate an organize its analysis basically to be able to answer to the important quarry's business questions. Using data queries the processed information is displayed on dashboards by the Microsoft PowerBI tool that can be run locally.

<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>This service is aimed at helping the quarry managers and operators to get insights on the one hand, on how good the quality of the material is that is extracted and is transported to the plant, and on the other, to get alarms that could prevent failures at the crusher level.</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>The most critical component parameters choice is about the camera, including industrial grade performance (outdoor temperature range and dust resistance) and optical lense characteristics. In this case, a camera that is able to take color (RGB) images and shape of material being transported on the conveyor belt running at 1,81 m/s. Additionally the working distance should be around 500mm.</p> <p>Then in order to feed the camera and implement the first image selection and processing steps, an industrial computer had to be chosen able to withstand a harsh industrial environment: extreme temperatures, dust and slight vibrations (housing allowing sufficient temperature dissipation), to integrate cellular modem. An I7 processor with 12M of cache RAM was chosen with PCIe bus and connectors.</p> <p>About the communications the network was chosen based on the network coverage reaching the quarry location that is at the moment 4G.</p>

	<p>The network provider and thus the SIM used is from Telefonica/Movistar the incumbent operator in Spain that has a reliable IoT network for industrial applications running on a specific network infrastructure. A VPN is established between the controlling PC in the Quarry and a server connected to a NAS at the SIGMA premises.</p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>Cameras had to be installed and fixed on the most appropriate locations to get good quality images. Two cameras are used as mentioned above and pictures of their installation is shown in figures 5 and 6. First in figure 21, the primary crusher cameras location is pinpointed at the quarry site level. The material is transported to the place marked with an orange square.</p> <p>The material is firstly classified using a roller screen before entering the primary jaw crusher.</p> <p>Now let's describe and precise the cameras installation process and requirements followed.</p> <p><i>Figure 23 Crusher's camera image</i></p>

Figure 24 Second camera installation position and different control, power and communication hardware installed on the crusher controlling cabin.

In order to install all the elements that have been described and shown above, SIGMA has to subcontract A Valdilecha’s certified installer who has been active in the quarry since its foundation. That was key in order to place all the material in positions that were possible to reach with the cabling following the given electrical parameters. All this under the near scrutiny from the CEMEX managers. SIGMA supervised all the procedure and performed the final tuning in terms of functional tests.

<p>Communication Protocols -</p>	<p>Locally every element is cabled and using for the camera PoE type of connection able to transmit also power to the cameras. In this way cabling was easier to implement.</p> <p>To transmit the information from the quarry to the SIGMA servers in the cloud 4G technology is used over the Telefonica Movistar IoT solution: the Kite platform (https://telefonicatech.com/en/solutions/iot-connectivity/connectivity-services/kite-platform). It can be highlighted that “The Kite Platform solution has a dedicated global network infrastructure that’s integrated into the networks of the partner operators (In Spain Movistar 4G) and managed by cloud-hosted software that allows access via a web portal or a set of APIs from anywhere in the world”. A VPN was established between the quarry PC and a SIGMA server. Using a Rest API images are downloaded to NAS at SIGMA. Then via internet protocols AI processed data is transmitted to the IQS of DEQ (Datalake and Data Warehouse)</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>As mentioned above Data transfer from the quarry is secured via a VPN and data is stored locally in a SIGMA’s NAS. Then the data storage at the IQS is guaranteed by the AWS and Google cloud</p>

	<p>services. For identity and access management to the elements of the IQS, an opensource tool was used (Keycloak1). The details of the IQS components and management can be found in D4.22.</p>
<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>In the following figure the different image processing AI algorithms are depicted:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 25. AI CV Algorithms flowchart for material quality determination</i></p> <p>The details about the implementation of the above image processing blocks and algorithms can be found in D4.33</p>
<p>Application Features</p>	<p>The quality service has as main objective to provide to the quarry manager and operators a tool to visually observe, in the form of two different dashboards, the proportion of limestone that is effectively entering the plant and being processed on the one hand. And on the other, an additional dashboard is provided that determines the occupation of the conveyor belt. Threshold of the occupation is programmable to show possible overloading which normally ends by stopping the crusher process. The dashboards that were created are shown below:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 26 Material quality dashboard</i></p>

1 <https://www.keycloak.org/>
 2 D4.2: "Report on IQS design and architecture"
 3 D4.3: "Report on AI Algorithms and Services", p. 36-p.46.

With the quality dashboard, the concentration of clay on the material processed by the plant can be immediately observed based on programmable date span. The lighter color corresponds to the limestone detected by the CV algorithms applied to the crusher and conveyor belt images. Additionally, on the lower right side, the weather forecast is displayed since it can impact considerably the plant operation.

Figure 27 Occupation dashboard

The occupation dashboard shows on a per date basis, the occupation of the roller screen before the jaw crusher. Moreover, it provides an easy means to observe when big rocks have entered the crusher causing to stop the process. All events are recorded and valuable insight is provided on how important is the material processing at the exploitation quarry front and help on the decision-making process for improvement on the production rate.

An additional dashboard has been created, to gather abnormal events that have been detected during the processing of image data:

Date	Service	Description	Priority
16/01/2024 9:30:00	Quality	Oversize	High
16/01/2024 11:15:00	Grain Size	>40	High

Figure 28 Events dashboard for quality and granulometry services

Security & Compliance

In this service the images and videos taken do not contain any personal information and thus no conflict is perceived towards the data privacy regulations in Europe.

Performance Metrics

- **Throughput uptime** that in this case represents how good has the system performed during a working shift at the plant in terms of up time. Until now it reaches almost 100%.

$$\text{Throughput uptime} = \frac{\text{Total hours AI system uptime}}{\text{Time period}}$$

- **Mean time between failures** that measures the average time the system operates before a failure occurs. Until now the system **has been operating for more than 18 months and no failure has been detected.**

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operator intervention rate that measures how often human operators need to intervene to reactivate the service. In this case, during the last 18th months, two times a reset had to be performed by the operator.
Support & Maintenance	<p>The system is very stable and up to now and the support needed is minimal. The system is autonomous and can be also operated remotely. Troubleshooting until now has needed almost no effort. System reset has shown to solve all possible issues observed during the whole duration of the project.</p> <p>With respect to maintenance only optical lense cleaning has been needed a couple of times during all this time. This operation can be performed in a matter of minutes during a plant stop. The planning now is to implement the cleaning procedure every 3 months. It consumes around 10 minutes time and can be performed whenever the plant is not running.</p>
Business Model & Pricing	<p>Given the complexity of the technologies developed by the company, commercial management and technical management always go hand in hand, both in Sigma's beginnings and today, when defining the sales strategy for the commercialization of a new product. As a guideline, the following revenue model is established, although it will have to be adjusted according to the knowledge acquired in the pilot, and after a more in-depth analysis of market potential.</p> <p>Furthermore, since the actual implantation of the service will vary from quarry to quarry, it is complicated to provide accurate cost figures. The pricing below will be based on a deployment similar to the one carried out within the project.</p> <p>Thus, the pricing of the service will account for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial feasibility analysis: quarry and extracted material study to determine how quality is defined and to identify hardware requirements: 3.000 - 5.000 €. • Deployment fee: highly dependent on previous point. Average: around 20.000 €. • O&M fee: 3.000 € annually.
Competitive Advantage	<p>The Quality Determination service offers an innovative method to analyze the quality of a quarry's input material. This information, while useful on its own, is one of the first steps towards automated operation, since it enables modifying the processing speed of the site.</p> <p>The service uses a novel approach, based on computer vision, that is not found in any other commercially available product. This reliance on cameras makes for an easy to install solution that does not greatly impact the normal operation of the quarry.</p> <p>Last but not least, the system can help predict possible blockages of the crusher, allowing operators to anticipate the problems thus reducing downtime.</p> <p>It should be noted that the partnership with the UPM university, mining and geology faculty experts, makes the offering very competitive since the know-how on minerology and mining is key to personalize the service depending on the type of material processed and the fabrication processes employed in a given quarry.</p>
Future Enhancements	<p>There are certainly attractive upgrades to be implemented over the models already in place:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction of other internal variables to make a combined data analysis with respect to costs and production variables already available at the quarry management system procedures. 2. Introduction of external variables to determine how the quality is influenced for example by the weather statistics and forecasts. Another possibility is to analyze data from the

	mining industry with respect to the foreseen use of materials for example in construction that could impact the production directly.
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2.3.2.1.1.2 *Activities performed since November 2023*

The computer vision system installation as described in the above section was completed in November of 2023 and reported on D4.3. Since then, almost no physical intervention was needed in the plant since the system proved to be very reliable. Most of the efforts since then were devoted to the improvement of the AI models used to determine the quality of the material using two cameras as described in the previous section.

As for the model improvement, the most relevant achievements are below outlined which represent the continuous AI engineering effort that has been carried out.

- **Improvement of the AI modelling techniques on the images obtained at the crusher**

The goal of the improvements were to generate high-precision segmentation masks with minimal manual annotations. Traditional segmentation methods rely heavily on fully supervised learning, making data annotation costly and time-consuming. The proposed approach leverages **weakly supervised learning**, integrating machine-generated pseudo-labels, **Variational Autoencoders (VAE)** for background normalization, and a **U-Net segmentation model**.

Figure 29 Crusher images at noon (sunlight)

The primary challenge addressed was **environmental variability**—lighting conditions, dust, and texture variations—that affect the accuracy of segmentation models because the quality of the images is impacted as can be seen below. The pipeline aims to minimize manual annotation efforts while maintaining high-quality segmentation performance.

Proposed Segmentation Pipeline

The pipeline follows a **multi-stage approach** combining pre-processing, weak supervision, and fine-tuning with limited high-quality annotations.

1. Image Preprocessing

Images are captured by the crusher camera. then the following steps were applied to the images: a **grayscale conversion**, a **histogram equalization (CLAHE)**, and finally a **gamma correction** to enhance image quality. At the end, the latter normalizes lighting and background variations to reduce segmentation errors.

The result of the preprocessing is shown below:

Figure 30 Image preprocessing results on the crusher roller screen

2. Pseudo-Label Generation Using VAE

A VAE-based **background model** is trained on images of an empty crusher roller screen. The reconstructed background is subtracted from images containing ore to estimate foreground regions. At the same time, classical background subtraction methods (e.g., Median, KNN, GMM) were tested but failed due to extreme environmental variability.

3. U-Net Segmentation Model

The U-Net architecture is used for segmentation due to its effectiveness in handling fine-grained object boundaries. A small **set of 50 high-quality annotated images** was selected using **Vision Transformer (ViT)-based clustering**. Data augmentation was applied to improve model generalization.

4. Human-in-the-Loop Fine-Tuning

CVAT and SAM (Segment Anything Model) were used for semi-automatic annotation. Annotators refined segmentation masks for a sparse set of images. Then an iterative fine-tuning is performed to improve segmentation accuracy, particularly for large rock detection.

The pipeline is shown below as a pipeline that includes the training process:

Figure 31 Complete data pipeline for the segmentation employed for the images of the crusher.

At the end, to summarize the results obtained after the use of the latter techniques: A dataset of **81,000 images** was collected under varying lighting and weather conditions. A small subset of **50 representative images** was manually annotated. To evaluate the results, the following metrics were applied: **Intersection over Union (IoU)** that measures the overlap between predicted and ground truth masks, and **Precision** that assesses the proportion of correct segmentations among all detected foreground regions. Moreover an ablation study was performed which evaluates how each of the elements of the pipeline contributes to the final result. It was demonstrated that the combined approach (**pseudo-labels + fine-tuning with high-quality annotations**) achieved the best results. In the following figure the segmentation results obtained from an original image down to the one where the advanced segmentation was applied.

Figure 32 Advanced segmentation performed over the images obtained at the Valdilecha's crusher

The proposed conveyor belt segmentation pipeline effectively reduces annotation efforts while maintaining high segmentation accuracy.

- **Improvement of the AI modelling techniques on the images obtained at the C3 conveyor belt**

For the C3 conveyor belt images also efforts were conducted in order to improve the segmentation results. The first efforts were devoted to the use of a supervised deep learning segmentation approach where an important manual effort had to be carried out over the image annotation (the results were reported in D4.3).

In a second phase, advanced segmentation models were tested thoroughly. YOLO and FastSAM models were used.

YOLO4 is a real time object detection algorithm that approached the problem as a regression rather than a classification task by spatially separating bounding boxes and associating probabilities to each detected image using a single convolutional neural network (CNN). It was introduced in 2015 and since then many versions have been created. Version 8 was chosen to carry out the experiments.

FastSAM is an improved version of SAM (Segment Anything Model introduced by Meta in 2023) it also with a high degree of precision, generates masks that segment objects in an image. Its main advantage is that it is trained with only 2% of the data used to train the original SAM model.

in order to discard the belt background from the material that is transported, the most relevant result is shown below.

Figure 33 Segmented image form C3 separating the belt background form the transported material

Fast SAM was tested to segment the limestone rocks using prompts that guide the process in the model. The result was not very stable as can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 34 FastSAM segmentation results

4 [YOLO paper](#)

- Generation of the Dashboards using the IQS components and visualization with PowerBI

The AI models output is generated via json files daily that are inserted at the end in form of tables into the Data Warehouse. The latter data is displayed in the Dahboards generated in PowerBI as shown in Figure 26 and Figure 27.

So the work at this stage was centered in the implementation of the pipeline displayed in the picture below:

Figure 35 Data pipeline including the IQS components in order to generate Dashboards

More precisely on the programming of the ETL block and the queries at the Data Warehouse . The latter extract the data from the Data Warehouse organized tables in a way that can be shown in a user friendly manner at the PowerBI tool. The ETL block is mode out from scripts that use the CDMP component of the Datalake(2) to get the uncompressed data that are meaningful for the AI services results displaying.

The occupation dashboard (Figure 27) was not originally planned, but when the results of the segmentation models was analyzed, the possibility of generating such a dashboard was discussed with Cemex that showed a great interest and thus it was created.

2.3.2.1.2 Grain size determination (Granulometry) Service

2.3.2.1.2.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	GRAIN SIZE DETERMINATION SERVICE (GRANULOMETRY)
Overview	<p>The characteristics of aggregates are determined by their geometric, physical, chemical, and durability properties. One of the key factors in classifying the final product of aggregates is the size of the particles that make up the material. Both the input materials that are fed into the fragmentation machinery and the output products obtained from it need to be defined based on the size of the particles.</p> <p>The aim of this AI service is to automate the process of determining whether the treated material meets technical specifications. By analyzing the screening efficiency, it can quickly identify any issues with the screening process. This allows for timely repairs or replacements of screens, ensuring the proper functioning of material treatment processes.</p> <p>For this purpose, we used computer vision techniques by installing a camera in a conveyor belt carrying the produced material to the final product stockpiles. According to the indications of the Quarry Director, the focus was set on the material with a grain size between 4/20 mm.</p> <p>In the following Valdilecha’s secondary phase plant diagram, the camera installation placement is pinpointed with and orange square, on the C33 conveyor belt.</p>

Figure 36 Valdilecha's secondary schematic configuration and camera positioning

Moreover; a picture of the physical location of the secondary within a complete view of the quarry is shown:

Figure 37 Valdilecha's secondary location in the quarry

The main objective of this service is to determine whether materials with a size greater than the upper limit (20 mm) are detected in order to generate alarms or warnings regarding the correct functioning of the entire process. In this sense, it could indicate a malfunction of the crusher or excessive wear of the sieves.

Additionally, a secondary objective is the approximate automatic determination of the actual granulometric curve of the processed material. In this regard, the real granulometric curve is calculated from the weight of the fragments of various size ranges. Since cameras are being used to determine the number of materials in each size range, one issue to be resolved is the weight they represent. To do this, various samples of material were taken from the stockpiles to establish the granulometric curves in the laboratory. Once the materials of each size range were separated, they were manually counted, weighed and their volume determined in order to determine the average weight and average volume of each size range. Thus, it was possible to transfer the direct conversion from the density and volume values to the automatic calculation of sizes using

	<p>computer vision, obtaining a good approximation to reality. Nevertheless, the automatic counting of small fragments sometimes is not clear, since they are usually at the bottom of the conveyor belt and covered by larger fragments. In this regard, it is the only part where the curve is separated from the real value.</p>
<p>Key Components</p>	<p>The main HW components are represented in the following architecture diagram:</p> <p><i>Figure 38. Granulometry service component architecture in the quarry</i></p> <p>The components are: one camera, an industrial PC (with modem + external antenna, PCI board to interface and power the camera, SIM card) and two LED arrays which will be used to have a controlled lighting environment at the conveyor area. As can be seen, exactly the same components were used here in comparison to the quality determination service, but using only one camera and without a computer monitor because there is no operator working in that crusher booth. With respect to the global architecture including the transmission of the data to the IQS components an identical architecture is used as the one shown in (Figure 20 Component architecture). This means, that an industrial PC was also used to control the camera which integrates a 4G modem and uses a SIM from the Telefonica IoT network, to transmit over a VPN channel the data captured to the local server at SIGMA. The AI processed data is then stored on the datalake and then filtered and organized on the Data Warehouse in specific tables. The granulometry dashboards were also designed in PowerBI which extracts the data from the Data Warehouse.</p>
<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>This service is aimed at helping the quarry managers and operators to get insights on the one hand, on how good the quality of the material is that is produced by the plant of given dimensions, and on the other, to get indications that could give insights about possible defects on the final steps of the production.</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>The hardware requirements in this case are exactly the same as for the quality determination service listed in section (2.3.2.1.1).</p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>For this service only one camera had to be installed as mentioned earlier over the C33-conveyor belt to analyze the images of the produced material of the dimensions 4/20 mm. The camera had to be connected to the controlling PC installed at a booth in the vicinity of the conveyor belt. Below the positioning of both elements are marked on an image taken at Validilecha (In yellow the positions are marked).</p>

Figure 39 Installation points of the camera (left) and PC components (right).

The camera was installed together with a couple of lighting diode arrays as shown in Figure 38. Moreover, the camera is covered by a canvas ensuring stable lighting conditions. The 4G antenna and the power supply were both also installed at the booth. The figure below shows photographs of the latter installation components.

	<p><i>Figure 40. Pictures of the camera, antenna and power supply installed at the Valdilecha's secondary.</i></p> <p>In order to install all the elements that have been described and shown above, SIGMA had to subcontract a Valdilecha's certified installer who has been active in the quarry since its foundation (same as for the quality determination service).</p>
<p>Communication Protocols -</p>	<p>Locally every element is cabled and using for the camera PoE type of connection able to transmit also power to the cameras. In this way cabling was easier to implement.</p> <p>To transmit the information from the quarry to the SIGMA servers in the cloud 4G technology is used over the Telefonica Movistar IoT solution: the Kite platform (https://telefonicatech.com/en/solutions/iot-connectivity/connectivity-services/kite-platform). It can be highlighted that "The Kite Platform solution has a dedicated global network infrastructure that's integrated into the networks of the partner operators (In Spain Movistar 4G) and managed by cloud-hosted software that allows access via a web portal or a set of APIs from anywhere in the world". A VPN was established between the quarry PC and a SIGMA server. Using a Rest API images are downloaded to NAS at SIGMA. Then via internet protocols AI processed data is transmitted to the IQS of DEQ (Datalake and Data Warehouse).</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>As mentioned above Data transfer from the quarry is secured via a VPN and data is stored locally in a SIGMA's NAS. Then the data storage at the IQS is guaranteed by the AWS and Google cloud services. For identity and access management to the elements of the IQS, an opensource tool was used (Keycloaks). The details of the IQS components and management can be found in D4.2</p>
<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>In the figure below the computer vision processes implemented for this granulometry service are shown.</p> <pre> graph LR A[C4-20 conveyor belt] --> B[Image input] B --> C[Image preprocessing] C --> D[Segmentation] D --> E[Distribution calculation] subgraph Image_processing [Image processing] C D E end </pre>

5 <https://www.keycloak.org/>

	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 41. AI processes used for the service</i></p> <p>The details about the implementation of the above image processing blocks and algorithms can be found in D4.3. And the refinement of the process is explained in the next section.</p>
	<p>The granulometry service has as main objective to provide to the quarry manager and operators a tool to visually observe, in the form of two different dashboards. The first one shows the granulometry curve that in fact shows three curves, one representing the percentage of the minimal size material observed, another one showing the percentage of the maximum size particles observed and a third curve representing the percentage of the calculated area of different particles observed. It should be mentioned that to develop the mathematical model governing this dashboard, a correction factor was investigated taking as a reference on the one hand the results obtained by Cemex in the laboratory (manual process being implemented periodically at the moment), and on the other by analyzing physical samples that have been taken on the quarry for the relevant stock size. In this way a comparison could be done using the AI CV processed data obtained and the ground truth obtained with the samples. Here follows the implemented dashboard.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 43 Number of particles observed Dashboard</i></p> <p>Both dashboards have as input variable the time period where the results want to be observed</p>
<p>Application Features</p>	
<p>Security & Compliance</p>	<p>- Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data. - Compliance with industry regulations (GDPR, HIPAA, etc.).</p>

	<p>In this service the images and videos taken do not contain any personal information and thus no conflict is perceived towards the data privacy regulations in Europe</p>
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p>- KPIs to measure success (e.g., system uptime, AI model accuracy, data processing speed).</p> <p>The KPIs are very similar to the ones taken into consideration for the quality service:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Throughput uptime that in this case represents how good has the system performed during a working shift at the plant in terms of up time. Until now it reaches almost 100%. $\text{Throughput uptime} = \frac{\text{Total hours AI system uptime}}{\text{Time period}}$ • Mean time between failures that measures the average time the system operates before a failure occurs. Until now the system has been operating for more than 18 months and no failure has been detected. • Operator intervention rate that measures how often human operators need to intervene to reactivate the service. <p>In this case, during the last 18th months, one time only a reset had to be performed by the operator.</p>
<p>Support & Maintenance</p>	<p>The system is very stable and up to now and the support needed is minimal. The system is autonomous and can be also operated remotely. Troubleshooting until now has needed almost no effort. System reset has shown to solve all possible issues observed during the whole duration of the project.</p> <p>With respect to maintenance only optical lense cleaning has been needed even less frequently than for the camera on the crusher (every 3 to 4 months is ok). This operation can be performed in a matter of minutes during a plant stop. The planning now is to implement the cleaning procedure every 3 months. It consumes around 10 minutes time and can be performed whenever the plant is not running.</p>
<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>The Grain Size service offers a solution to continuously monitoring the size distribution of an end product. It is based solely on images captured by cameras located on the belt of interest, so it can be deployed without too much effect in the quarry operation. Its innovative algorithms, refined thanks to laboratory experiments conducted on the material, are capable of estimating the size of occluded layers, improving its accuracy compared to similar solutions in the market. Lastly, having a way to constantly monitor the belt helps predict and identify issues in the sieves, reducing potential downtime.</p> <p>Given the complexity of the technologies developed by the company, commercial management and technical management always go hand in hand, both in Sigma's beginnings and today, when defining the sales strategy for the commercialization of a new product. As a guideline, the following revenue model is established, although it will have to be adjusted according to the knowledge acquired in the pilot, and after a more in-depth analysis of market potential.</p> <p>Furthermore, the implementation carried out within the project monitors only one conveyor belt. Potential future implementations might include a higher number of belts, increasing the deployment and maintenance cost.</p> <p>Thus, the pricing of the service will account for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial material analysis: material study to determine a-priori size distribution and other characteristics to refine the algorithms: 1.000 -3.000 €. • Deployment fee: 5.000 – 10.000 € per belt, plus 5.000 € for processing hardware.

	O&M fee: 3.000 € annually.
Competitive Advantage	<p>Some competitors can be found in the granulometry market. The most relevant are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WipFrag: this company offers PSD (Particle Size Distribution) software to analyze digital images. It can process images collected at the muck pile, stockpile or laboratory samples, or drone/UAV images. However, it does not offer a fixed system capable of keeping a history of the size distribution at a certain point, without manual intervention. - Mine Prism: they also offer PSD software, in this case focused on images captured by a smartphone, which, as in the previous case, does not allow to keep an automated history of the material. They also offer a fixed hardware system but, due to its complexity, its deployment is not as simple as in the Grain Size service. <p>Other competitors, such as OreScan, also offer material characterization but focused on the pre-blast, which differs from the solution offered by the Grain Size service.</p> <p>Moreover, it should be noted that the service comprises the expert analysis of the produced material carried out by the Polytechnic university of Madrid (Geology and mining department)</p>
Future Enhancements	<p>Since the models that have been revisited the last period, an important improvement lies on the analysis of the data set that has been used for training the segmentation model and enriching it with the images that are continuously been recorded. The focus will be on identifying images that can be classified as representative of problems that are occurring during production, especially in screens.</p>

2.3.2.1.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

The activities performed were meant to improve the overall process of the data and conversations were held with CEMEX in order to assess the value of the solution obtained. In the figure below the comparison of the AI based approach to calculate the granulometry with the manual approach performed until now is sketched.

Figure 44 A) the AI based granulometry service pipeline. B) Traditional approach

A clear methodology was put in place for the AI based approach:

1. Dataset generation: Image data description and data generation pipeline.
2. Segmentation model: Exploration of the segmentation model used for the image analysis. Initial study, Training and Inference will be explained.
3. Granulometry generation: Usage of the segmentation data to produce the granulometry. Fundamental study and experiments will be explained.
4. Information sharing: Pipeline for info sharing with the quarrying enterprise. Details of the infrastructure.

The capture process of the data was improved, which is now based on the accurate pixel-to-millimeter conversion approach. To achieve this, we conducted a calibration procedure to establish a reliable spatial reference. The calibration dataset included objects of known dimensions and distinct colors, which served as ground truth for size estimation. Additionally, a checkerboard pattern was incorporated into the calibration process to facilitate geometric corrections and improve the accuracy of spatial mappings (Figure below).

Figure 45 Calibration dataset images for the AI based approach for size estimation of the particles.

The segmentation model choice process was extended and at the end the following models were studied and tested:

1. DexiNed6: Edge detection pipeline used for segmentation of fine-grain objects. It provides high resolution edge maps and is suitable for tasks requiring precise boundary delineation.
2. FastSAM7: A fast and efficient segmentation model optimized for real-time applications, providing rapid instance segmentation with minimal latency. It is designed for resource-constrained environments and offers a good trade-off between speed and accuracy.
3. YOLOWorld8: An advanced object detection model capable of open-vocabulary object recognition, allowing detection of a wide variety of object categories. It supports multi-modal inputs and is effective for both common and rare object detection tasks.
4. Yolo8seg9 : A lightweight, real-time instance segmentation model based on the YOLACT architecture, designed for high-speed segmentation tasks. It is suitable for applications requiring real-time performance and supports both object detection and mask segmentation simultaneously.

The last model is actually used.

Finally, the process that is followed to generate the granulometry curves was automated and below a schema represents the different steps that are being followed (Image Capture, Segmentation, limestone blob dimensional analysis with three different measures and data displaying).

6 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0031320323001619?via%3Dihub>

7 <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.12156>

8 <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.17270>

9 <https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.02689>

Figure 46 Granulometry generation processes

2.3.3 BIM integration (Task 4.4.)

2.3.3.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	BIM Integration & Management
Overview	Implement Building Information Modeling (BIM) strategies at CEMEX Valdilecha to enhance operational efficiency, planning, and management throughout the quarry lifecycle. This involved creating 3D digital representations (Digital Twins) of the quarry, developing 4D simulations for long-term planning (including exploitation and restoration phases), performing schedule risk analysis, and establishing a 7D model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) connected to real-time data for asset management and monitoring.
Key Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3D BIM Models: IFC models of the treatment plant, mobile machinery, and quarry topography including exploitation volumes, based on drone data, CAD files, and photos. - 4D BIM Planning Tool: Asta Powerproject used to develop long-term schedules (documentation, exploitation, restoration), link them to the BIM model, calculate activity durations based on volumes and resource allocation (mobile machinery), and visualize the quarry lifecycle. - Risk Analysis Module: Integrated within the planning tool to perform quantitative schedule risk analysis (Monte Carlo simulation) based on DCMA standards. - CDE Platform: Tandem deployed as a central repository, linking BIM models with static asset data and dynamic operational data (plant

	<p>production/consumption, mobile machinery cycles) from the DataLake.</p> <p>Data Integrator: Custom tool to fetch data from the DataLake API and update the CDE.</p>
Target Audience	Quarry Management, Planning Engineers, Operations Managers, Environmental Managers.
Hardware Requirements	<p>For CDE/4D Plan access: Standard PC with internet access.</p> <p>For Mobile App: Compatible smartphone (details not specified, assumed standard Android/iOS).</p>
Installation Process	- 3D/4D Model & CDE Setup: Performed by APP Consultoría, involving model creation/conversion, schedule development, risk analysis setup, CDE configuration, and DataLake integration.
Communication Protocols -	<p>- DataLake to CDE: HTTPS via API calls by the integrator.</p> <p>- User Access to CDE/Planning Tools: Standard HTTPS.</p>
Data Storage & Management	<p>- BIM Models/4D Plan/Risk Analysis: Stored within respective software (Revit, Asta Powerproject) and exported as standard formats (IFC, project files).</p> <p>- CDE Data: Stored within Autodesk Tandem (cloud platform), including model geometry, static asset data, and ingested dynamic data from DataLake.</p>
AI Integration & Implementation	While APP's core work focused on BIM/4D/CDE, the CDE serves as a platform to integrate and visualize data potentially generated or used by AI services from other partners (WP4). No direct AI model development within T4.4 by APP is mentioned for CEMEX in D4.5.
Application Features	<p>- BIM Model: Accurate 3D representation of quarry assets and terrain.</p> <p>- 4D Planning: Long-term lifecycle simulation, progress tracking comparison (baseline vs. actual), resource allocation analysis</p> <p>- Risk Analysis: Probabilistic schedule forecasting</p> <p>- CDE: Interactive 3D model navigation (walk-through), asset data viewing (static & dynamic), data filtering, historical data charting, customizable dashboards</p>
Security & Compliance	- CDE Access: Managed via Autodesk Tandem user authentication.
Performance Metrics	-
Support & Maintenance	APP Consultoría provides training and support for the CDE and associated tools during the pilot phase.

Business Model & Pricing	- Subscription-based (less than 150k euro/year -> approx. 20k Euro for the software licenses and 120k Euro for the maintenance and update of services).
Competitive Advantage	Comprehensive integration of BIM dimensions (3D, 4D, 7D) tailored for quarry lifecycle management. Includes long-term planning, quantitative risk analysis, and a live Digital Twin (CDE) connected to operational data sources. Provides enhanced visualization and data access for informed decision-making
Future Enhancements	Refinement of data integration workflows. Expansion of CDE dashboards based on user needs. Continued use of 4D planning and risk analysis for ongoing operations and restoration planning. Deeper integration with other digital tools used at the quarry.

2.3.3.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Following the development and reporting of the initial BIM models, 4D long-term plans, risk analysis, and CDE setup in Deliverable D4.5, the activities for CEMEX Valdilecha focused on the deployment, refinement, and handover of these tools:

- **CDE Deployment and Data Integration:** The Common Data Environment (CDE) platform (Autodesk Tandem) for Valdilecha was finalized and populated with the relevant BIM models (treatment plant, mobile machinery, topography). Static asset data was incorporated. The custom data integrator was activated to pull dynamic data streams (Plant Production, Plant Consumption, Mobile Machinery Cycles) from the central DataLake and link them to the corresponding assets within the CDE. Data visualization dashboards within the CDE were configured to display this integrated data.
- **4D Planning & Risk Analysis Handover:** The developed long-term 4D BIM plan (covering documentation, exploitation, and restoration phases) and the associated schedule risk analysis results were finalized and prepared for handover. This included the work programme structure, resource allocation logic, duration calculations, and the probabilistic finish date forecasts (P10/P50/P90).
- **Training and Support:** Access to the CDE platform was granted to the CEMEX team. Initial support and guidance were provided to familiarize the team with the CDE functionalities, data visualization, and the potential uses of the integrated BIM tools for operational oversight and planning.

2.3.4 Quarry Voices on Technology Deployment

The following section presents a structured interview conducted by ANEFA, as the coordinator of the DigiEcoQuarry project. The interview aimed to gather qualitative feedback from representatives of Valdilecha concerning the technologies implemented at their site. The primary objectives included assessing overall perception, operational impacts, observed benefits, key success factors, potential barriers, and suggestions for future enhancements. Insights gained from this discussion provide valuable understanding regarding the effectiveness of technological innovations developed by the project, their replicability within the industry, and their alignment with broader sustainability goals.

1. Overall Perception

General assessment of implemented technologies:

Cemex provided positive feedback regarding the implemented technologies, highlighting their practical benefits. Key technologies included advanced sensors for measuring colour and granulometry, which enabled early detection of contamination or deviations in material quality during production. Additionally, automated alert systems were established to promptly indicate any faults or deviations, enhancing production reliability. Improved monitoring of mobile machinery

significantly boosted fleet management by providing detailed insights into diesel consumption, machinery utilization, and operational performance.

Moreover, comprehensive drilling and blasting studies were conducted, identifying critical areas for operational improvement, particularly in blast geometry precision and explosive usage. Recommendations from these studies contributed significantly to operational efficiency and safety.

Added value to daily operations:

Implemented technologies substantially enhanced daily operations by proactively identifying potential issues, enabling timely interventions, and ensuring consistent high-quality final products. Automation streamlined routine processes, allowing personnel to engage in analytical and value-added tasks, thus elevating overall operational effectiveness.

2. Key Benefits Observed

Operational efficiency: Technologies facilitated efficient fleet management, precise maintenance scheduling, improved blasting practices, and effective resource allocation, optimizing operational costs and productivity.

Environmental impact: Enhanced monitoring capabilities led to optimized diesel consumption, significantly reducing emissions. Better-designed blasts further supported sustainability by minimizing resource use and reducing environmental impacts.

Workplace safety: Technologies indirectly improved workplace safety, particularly through more accurate stockpile measurement systems and safer blasting practices, reducing worker exposure to hazardous situations.

Digitalization: Digitalization improvements provided valuable data-driven insights, leading to quicker and more informed decisions regarding machinery investments, maintenance planning, and production adjustments.

3. Success Factors and Adoption Potential

Ease of integration and user-friendliness: Cemex praised the intuitive and customized dashboard visualizations (Power BI), especially for granulometry and color measurement sensors, facilitating easy adoption and operational integration.

Replicability across different quarry sites: The team viewed the technologies as highly replicable across other Cemex quarries, recognizing universal benefits for enhancing efficiency and productivity.

Contribution to industry innovation: Valdilecha's quarry managers considered the implemented technologies highly innovative, significantly advancing the industry standard by automating processes, enhancing data management, optimizing resource use, and improving blasting operations. They emphasized the potential for broader industry adoption.

Barriers to adoption: Although recognizing substantial advantages, they highlighted high initial investment costs and extended return periods as potential barriers, particularly in existing operations with narrower profit margins.

4. Future Outlook

Recommendations and opportunities for further optimization: Due to the drilling and blasting studies, it was recommended to enhance blasting operations, particularly by improving the precision of geometry measurements for rock benches and increasing explosive efficiency. The quarry is currently working on these improvements.

Long-term implementation prospects: Participants identified excellent long-term potential, advocating strongly for adopting these technologies from inception in new quarry developments. They foresee significant operational, safety, and financial benefits from fully digitalized approaches.

Alignment with the sector's sustainability goals: Cemex crew affirmed that these technologies align fully with Cemex's sustainability and net-zero objectives, actively contributing to efficient resource utilization and reduced environmental impact.

3 Results and recommendations

The activities at the Valdilecha pilot site have involved supporting and implementing technologies, solutions, and research in collaboration with other project partners. As a pilot site, it has been crucial to share our expertise and deep understanding of the processes, thereby communicating the needs from a productive and operational perspective and identifying areas for improvement and directions for enhancing KPIs. The developed technologies have been successfully implemented, and we have conducted the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, as well as performed impact assessments for the entire value chain using standardized KPIs.

As a pilot site, it has been essential to share our knowledge of the processes, thus communicating the needs from a production and operational point of view and identifying where there is room for improvement and the directions to take in order to improve the KPIs. The first fundamental step in improving production performance (improving the KPIs) is to acquire sufficient data to better monitor the processes, thus also having enough information to calculate the KPIs and estimate the evolution of performance. Scales, sensors, and cameras have been installed, and in the future, the data will be sent automatically to the system to study process performance in detail.

This section describes the main results achieved in Valdilecha quarry from the project. They are connected with the excavation process: improvement of charging design, fragmentation and muckpile prediction, and impact of blasting in the downstream processes.

Operational recommendations that significantly improve the excavation through advanced drilling and blasting techniques are highlighted.

3.1 Results

3.1.1 Improvement of charging design based on drilling data

Three blasts from the second campaign (B-240507, B-240521 and B-240625) were successfully charged with RIOFLEX using the recommendation generated from the drilling data interpretation and the decking strategy (blasts charged with ANFO were not considered in the analysis). To assess the impact of the density reduction and decking strategies, the Z-score is calculated for the linear density in each hole, using the mean and standard deviation of their respective blast. This metric represents the variation of this parameter within the same blast, which should be reduced (Z-score close to zero) with the application of differential charging.

The boxplot in Figure 47 represents the distribution of Z-scores for the blasts charged with RIOFLEX without rock data (164 holes from seven blasts: B-230518, B-230530, B-230612, B-230621, B-230710, B-230714 and B-240404) and the three successfully charged ones with an adapted design (66 holes). Results indicate a lower variation in the linear density for the adapted blasting compared with the regular scheme (revealed by the median Z-score 0.07 versus -0.26 of the distributions). In addition, the number of outliers is reduced as structures impacting the amount of explosive mass are bypassed using the gasbag plugs during the second campaign.

Figure 47 Boxplot with Z-score distribution from linear density values for regular and adapted blasting schemes.

3.1.2 Fragmentation prediction model

A prediction model for blasting fragmentation was developed using data from 23 blasts at Valdilecha quarry. Its main application is to evaluate and predict the influence of aspects such as powder factor, blast design and rock mass block geometry on blasting performance in the quarry. The model is based on the fragmentation energy fan formulation, introduced by Ouchterlony et al. (2017).

Parameter fitting is performed via MATLAB using *fitlm* routine (MathWorks, 2013), which executes an ordinary non-linear least squares regression. The fit is carried out in log form (see Eq.1) with 1,296 observation points limited from percentile P_{90} , being the only point at which true fragmentation is known (i.e., the mass fraction passing as a function of the mesh size, determined by sieving and weighing) to $P=100\%$ in steps of 1.

$$\log \frac{x_P}{L_C} = \xi \log J_S + \omega \log J_0 + \log x_0^* - \alpha(P) \cdot [\log E + \log f_{C\Delta} + \lambda \log L_C - \beta \log \tilde{\sigma} - \log E_0^*] \quad (1)$$

Where x_P represents the fragment size for a percentile P , scaled by a characteristic length L_C , which is blast geometry dependent. E_0 and x_0 denote the coordinates of the convergence focus, E signifies the specific volumetric energy deposited, and $\alpha(P) = \alpha_{100} + (\alpha_{50} - \alpha_{100}) \cdot \left(\frac{100}{P} - 1\right)^{1/b}$ is the slope of the fan lines expressed as a function of the Swebrec parameter b , x_{100} and x_{50} . E_0^* and x_0^* are the ordinate and abscissa of the focal point, $f_{C\Delta}$ is the cooperation function of the delay, $\tilde{\sigma}$ represents the rock mass strength, J_S is the joint spacing factor, and J_0 is the joint orientation. λ , ξ and ω are non-negative constant parameters.

3.1.2.1 Energy

Explosive energy is the most influential blast design variable, and all fragmentation prediction formulae include it as a significant blast descriptor (Sanchidrián et al., 2022; Sanchidrián & Ouchterlony, 2023; Segarra et al., 2018, 2024). Figure

48 represents the borehole collar coordinates plotted according to a color scale, which indicates the amount of specific energy deposited in each blast; lighter colors represent higher energy.

Figure 48 Explosive energy (MJ/m³) employed in each blast is represented according to its magnitude. The higher powder factor is represented by yellow colours.

3.1.2.2 Blast design

Five characteristic lengths (Eqs. 2-6) have been proposed according to literature (Sanchidrián & Ouchterlony, 2017, 2023; Segarra et al., 2018, 2024). These lengths relate to the burden B (including the burden in the first row B_{r1}), spacing S , and height H , defines the blast design and allow for the non-dimensionalization of x_p by incorporating the effects of blast geometry in relation to fragmentation results (see Eq.1).

$$Lc = \sqrt{S \cdot H} \quad (2)$$

$$Lc = B \quad (3)$$

$$Lc = \sqrt{S \cdot B} \quad (4)$$

$$Lc = B_{r1} \quad (5)$$

$$Lc = \sqrt{S \cdot B_{r1}} \quad (6)$$

Another design variable that significantly affects fragmentation is the delay between consecutively fired holes or cooperation between holes (Ouchterlony et al. 2017). However, there is no variability in the detonation times (all blasts were fired with an in-row delay time of 42 ms except for only 240404 blast, fired with 17 ms), so it does not serve as a differentiating factor to explain the varying fragmentation. Therefore, $f_{c\Delta}$ is simplified in Eq.1.

3.1.2.3 Rock mass

MWD characterization provide insights into the rock's structural and strength response and can therefore be readily incorporated as a mechanical-related variable within the fragmentation prediction model. According to the results exposed in Deliverable D2.2 - TR6: Rock mass characterization in Valdilecha quarry using Measurement-While Drilling technology, FP is the MWD parameter that provide the best separation between MLIM, BLIM, and DLIM classes, being included as a

rock strength variable in Eq.1. It is understood that the strength of a MLIM rock is higher than DLIM. This deliverable also states that the structural characteristics of the rock mass are strongly influenced by variations in the drilling parameters. Therefore, variations of MWD parameters are proposed as variables describing the rock mass structure. Finally, J_0 factor in Eq. 1 is discarded.

For blasts without MWD data, values were extrapolated from surrounding drilling information. This approach is justified because MWD characteristics are relatively homogeneous within each pit zone. For example, blasts in the NE pit exhibit the highest FP values due to the dominance of massive limestone (MLIM), whereas zones in weaker rock formations show lower FP values such as SE pit (see Figure 49).

Figure 49 Average FP of each drillhole. Holes without available MWD data are marked in white.

Nonlinear fitting outputs are presented in Table 7. The local variations of the MWD parameters are analyzed for the J_s variable. Table 7 includes regression results using Eq.2 (this is the length that yields the most significant results), assessing the goodness-of-fit through the adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) and the mean absolute relative error (MARE) between the size-energy fan model predictions and the muckpile fragmentation sizes.

Table 7 Summary of free fragmentation energy-fan fitting parameters and performance.

J_s	L_c	Model parameters								Fitting performance	
		E_0^*	x'_0	α_{50}	b	α_{100}	λ	β	ξ	R^2	MARE
FPvar	$\sqrt{S \cdot H}$	5.68E-09	654.066	0.419	2.660	0.325	1.646	-0.765	0.043	0.940	0.085
RPvar		5.71E-09	649.371	0.441	2.659	0.342	1.612	-0.456	0.056	0.940	0.082
PRvar		2.62E-09	317.027	0.435	2.653	0.329	1.520	0.066	0.054	0.942	0.083
CPvar		4.69E-09	513.348	0.479	2.655	0.368	1.341	0.094	0.067	0.941	0.080

The fan fragmentation model demonstrates a strong fit to the experimental data, as evidenced by R^2 and MARE (refer to Table 7, Fitting Performance columns). No substantial differences are observed in the fits, with R^2 consistently around 0.94 and MARE yielding between 8-9%. The optimal fits are achieved using J_s as CPvar suggesting a positive correlation between

CP variations and fragmentation size, contrary to what might be reasonably expected. In this case, the strength-related coefficient β indicates that a massive rock (MLIM), requiring higher FP values for drilling, produce coarser fragmentation when blasting. Figure 50 represents $\alpha(P)$ (left) and the convergent focal position E_0^*, x_0^* (right) in a log-log scale where:

$$E^* = E \cdot L_c^\lambda / \bar{\sigma}^\beta \tag{7}$$

$$x_p^* = \frac{x_p / Lc}{J_s^\xi} \tag{8}$$

For the fitting interval ($P = 35\%$ to $P = 100\%$), this function is minimally oscillatory, causing the focal point to have a small abscissa E_0^* and a big ordinate x_0^* coordinates.

Figure 50 Left: Exponents of the percentile lines. Right: Rays extended to show the convergent pattern in log-log scale

Figure 51 shows the size-energy fan for this fit, where the scaled sizes of the percentiles x_p^* are plotted vs E^* . The plot illustrates the relatively good fitting of the model. The markers are shaped differently depending on their pit location: triangles for the NE Pit, circles for the N Pit, squares for the SE Pit, and hexagons for the NW Pit.

Figure 51 Fragmentation- energy fan model fitted to MSA fragmentation data. triangles for the NE Pit, circles for the N Pit, squares for the SE Pit, and hexagons for the NW Pit.

Figure 52 illustrates the MARE for each percentile, considering all blasts (thick line) and pits (thinner lines). Regarding the global MARE, the fragmentation data exhibited the best fit to the fragmentation model within a high percentile range (P = 42% to P = 92%), where MARE remains below 10% and stable. In the fines region, MARE is significantly higher, reaching up to 19%, although not all blasts include data for such low percentiles. Similarly, in the coarse fraction beyond P = 92%, MARE increases, deviating from the total MARE (8%, see Table 7) and reaching an error between 10 to 14%.

Overall, the blasts from the SE, NE, and NW pits maintain a low MARE, following a similar trend: MARE below 10% in the central range, with more pronounced increases at the extremes. However, blasts in the N pit show a clear different pattern, maintaining a relatively low MARE (below 15%) up to P = 50%, before a notable increase between P = 55% and P = 65%, reaching values of MARE 20-25%. Beyond P = 98%, errors rise further, reaching 25-30%.

Figure 52 MARE of blasts from N, NE, NW, and SE pits

In conclusion, the fragmentation-energy fan model demonstrated satisfactory performance in predicting fragment sizes across 23 blasts conducted at Valdilecha quarry. This result supports the approach to assess fragmentation under production constraints combining fragmentation measurements from 3D photogrammetric models with belt conveyor data in the primary crusher circuit. A key limitation of the methodology was the reliance on a single sieve data point (P₉₀) to correct photogrammetric muckpile data. Nonetheless, the results were promising, achieving R² exceeding 0.9 and a MARE of 8%.

3.1.3 Assessment of muckpile properties

The effect of blasting on the muckpile layout determined from aerial images of the pre- and post-blast surfaces and the measured paths of the blastholes was investigated in Section 7.1 of Deliverable D2.5. The approach consists of calculating sections of the pre- and post-blast triangulated surfaces from each of the holes of the last row in the direction of the rock motion. For each of these profiles, the displacement of the gravity center (GC) as from its positions before and after blasting, the swell, the drop, the spread and the slope are calculated, encompassing a sound description of the geometry of the muckpile.

This characterization was made for only one blast (230621) initiated with electronic detonators in which there is a high variability in the hole's confinement, and thus in the muckpile properties. This broad variation allows for a local analysis of the block and the muckpile geometry in different sections. The horizontal displacement of the GC, the slope and the swell factor of the muckpile are well predicted, R² > 0.88, with power/exponential functions of the effective burden of the first row or the bench stiffness ratio. The parameters calculated from these formulae (i.e. horizontal displacement of the GC,

slope, and final area – the latter calculated from the swell factor) are used to obtain trapezoidal sections fitting the muckpile profiles.

In order to provide more general prediction formulae for further control of the muckpile layout, five additional blasts are considered in this last stage of the project (see Table 8). These blasts were located in the North and Northeast pits of the quarry. They have about 20 holes drilled in two to four rows drilled parallel to the main highwall face; there is an additional lateral highwall face, significantly shorter than the main face of the block, in four blasts. The holes of the last row used for the analysis are shown in Table 8, increasing the database from 12 to 55 holes.

Table 8 General characteristics of the blasts considered to investigate muckpile properties.

Blast	Pit	MWD	Exp. & delay	Holes/Rows	Lateral Face	Holes last row ^a	Burden ^b , m		Height ^b , m	In-/Inter row delay, ms
							1 st row	All holes		
230621	N	No	New	28/3	No	H28-H18	7.9/3.8	4.9/3.8	13.1/0.9	42/109
230612	NE	Yes	New	26/4	Yes	H20-H26	5.9/1.0	4.6/0.5	15.4/0.6	42/67
230714	NE	Yes	New	28/3	Yes	H19-H28	4.8/1.0	4.6/0.5	12.7/2.7	42/109
230419	NE	No	Standard	16/2	Yes	H17-H10	5.6/1.5	5.5/1.2	14.0/1.0	42/107
230518	NE	Yes	New	24/3	No	H24-H16	5.4/1.4	4.8/1.1	13.5/1.0	42/151
230120	NE	No	Standard	24/2	Yes ^c	H24-H14	6.1/1.8	5.4/1.7	10.7/0.3	42/107

^aFirst and last hole initiated; ^bMedian and interquartile range from sections in direction perpendicular to the highwall face; ^cThe lateral highwall face is not well surveyed by the drone and the confinement conditions of hole H24 were unknown, so it is discarded.

To account for differences in the rock mass characteristics, the MWD pressures, the penetration rate and their moving variances (see section 3.2.1 in Deliverable D2.2, Appendix G) recorded in each hole are considered (see Table 9); for the two blasts in which MWD technology was not available (230419 and 230120), these values were extrapolated from the closest blasts with measured data, and they were then constant for all the holes, so the standard deviation is zero and it is not reported in Table 9. The moving variance of the parameters have a larger variability than the basic parameters, either pressures or penetration rate).

Table 9 Statistics (mean/standard deviation) of the MWD parameters from each hole of the last row for each blast and for all the dataset.

Parameter ^a	230621	230612	230714	230419	230518	230120	Min-Max	Av/std
FP (bar)	83.0/12	77.1/18.3	75.2/10.6	76.5	80.8/10.9	83.5	43.1-101.6	79.7/10.3
RP (bar)	63.9/4.9	61.9/7.2	61.5/4.2	63.5	62.3/4.1	64.3	48.8-75.6	63.0/4.0
PR (m/min)	2.0/0.5	2.0/0.7	2.3/0.4	2.2	1.8/0.4	1.7	1.0-3.1	2.0/0.4
CP (bar)	21.8/1.5	21.9/1.3	21.9/1.2	22	21.3/1.6	22	18.4-23.8	21.8/1.1
FPvar (bar ²)	306/52.3	304/223	265/31.2	123	266/567	165.3	117-719	238/104
RPvar (bar ²)	57.3/14.7	39.9/23.5	42.4/14.7	21.7	28/4.6	22.2	21.7-88.7	36.1/17.8
PRvar (m ² /min ²)	2.0/0.9	3.0/6.1	0.6/0.2	0.3	0.5/0.4	0.4	0.2-15.5	1.1/2.2
CPvar (bar ²)	4.6/3.0	4.2/5.5	2.6/2.3	0.8	1	0.6	0.1-14.0	2.3/2.9

^aFP: feed pressure; RP: rotation pressure; PR: penetration rate and compressor pressure and their moving variances (FPvar, RPvar, PRvar, and CPvar).

3.1.3.1 Block and muckpile properties

The profiles of the block and the muckpile are calculated for 53 holes of the last row in six blasts (two holes with different confinement than the other ones are discarded). The profiles are obtained along the directions defined by the movement vectors. Table 10 shows the geometrical characteristics for each hole of the last row calculated from the pre-blast profile. Table 10 also shows the hole dip and charging parameters, including the explosive energy rated as heat of explosion at constant volume. The total explosive mass delivered to the quarry and the nominal stemming length are used for blast 230120, while measured data for both parameters are available for the rest of the dataset.

Table 10 Statistics (mean/standard deviation) of the geometrical and charging parameters from each hole for each blast and for all the dataset.

Parameter ^a	230621	230612	230714	230419	230518	230120	Min-Max	Av/std
H (m)	12.6/0.9	15.1/0.7	12.9/1.3	13.4/0.9	13.4/0.8	10.7/0.2	10.4-15.7	12.8/1.5
Dh (°)	18.7/0.8	19.4/1.1	18.9/1.3	18.4/2.3	18.2/4.2	15.7/2.3	8.2-21.5	18.1/2.5
Effective horizontal burden along the direction of motion-Total								
b_{75}^* (m)	13.8/2.9	18.2/6.5	15.6/1.9	11.5/2.0	13.8/2.4	11.9/1.2	4.9-21.2	13.9/3.5
b_{50}^* (m)	13.3/2.4	17.9/6.4	14.9/2.9	11.1/2.0	13.3/2.3	11.3/1.1	4.7-20.7	13.4/3.5
Effective horizontal burden along the direction of motion - First row								
b_{50} (m)	8.2/1.7	6.1/0.9	6.5/2.1	6.4/0.8	6.3/1.3	6.3/0.9	4.5-10.4	6.7/1.6
b_{75} (m)	7.6/1.5	5.8/0.8	5.7/1.6	6.2/0.8	5.9/1.2	5.8/0.8	4.2-9.9	6.2/1.4
Charging								
M_e (kg)	217/14.9	152/15.3	165/7.0	140/20.7	164/40.7	140	65.3-256	166/34.3
ρ_l (kg/m)	13.8/1.6	13.3/0.6	15.7/0.7	14.0/1.4	16.3/1.2	12.5	12.1-18.7	14.3/1.7
Qv (MJ/kg)	2.854	2.854	2.854	3.776	2.854	3.776	-	-

^a H: bench height; D_h : hole dip; b_P^* : P percentile of the total effective burden; b_P : P percentile of the effective burden of the first row; M_e : mass of explosive; ρ_l : linear explosive density; and Qv: heat of explosion at constant volume.

The post-blast sections are used to calculate, the muckpile properties defined in Deliverable D2.5 (see more information on the calculation procedure in Section 7.1 on D2.5). Their main statistics (mean and standard deviation) are shown in Table 11.

Table 11 Statistics (mean/standard deviation) of the muckpile properties for each blast and for all the dataset.

Blast	230621	230612	230714	230419	230518	230120	Min-Max	Av/std
Hor. disp. GC, dx (m)	3.12/1.5	4.94/1.37	4.1/1.15	3.68/1.42	3.86/1.59	1.65/0.76	0.78-7.27	3.43/1.6
Vert. disp GC, dy (m)	0.94/0.56	1.73/0.59	1.29/0.58	2.02/0.36	1.26/0.39	0.56/0.29	0.13-2.87	1.24/0.66
2D disp. GC, dxy (m)	3.27/1.59	5.24/1.48	4.32/1.24	4.25/1.26	4.07/1.62	1.75/0.80	0.82-7.82	3.67/1.68
Swell factor, SF	1.28/0.17	1.4/0.44	1.26/0.08	1.15/0.18	1.30/0.14	1.11/0.08	0.78 ^a -2.30	1.24/0.2
Av. slope, κ	0.66/0.19	0.46/0.05	0.45/0.04	0.51/0.11	0.55/0.12	0.86/0.25	0.4-1.27	0.60/0.21
Range, dmax (m)	26.6/3.1	39.7/6.4	33.4/3.3	27.1/6.6	37.9/5.3	22.2/5.7	12.6-47.4	30.3/7.8
Drop, D (m)	1.57/0.93	1.56/0.69	1.99/0.92	2.34/0.48	1.23/0.61	1.26/0.37	0.05-3.36	1.65/0.79

^aH10 adjacent to the lateral highwall face in blast 230419 has an atypical small swell factor below one, of 0.78. The next smallest value is slightly above the unity.

To describe qualitatively the muckpile sections observed, six categories obtained from percentiles 2.5, 25, 75 and 97.5 of the slope of the muckpile (i.e., equivalent to the angle of repose) are defined; they are quantitatively qualified as very flat (κ

< 0.4, percentile 2.5), flat ($\kappa = 0.4-0.45$, percentiles 2.5-25), intermediate ($\kappa = 0.45-0.68$, percentiles 25-75), steep ($\kappa = 0.68-1.25$, percentiles 75-97.5), and very steep ($\kappa > 1.25$, percentiles 97.5). An example for each of them is shown in Figure 53; note that the brown color is just the mixture of green (block) and red (muckpile). The respective swell factor given in the top right corner do not decrease monotonically for the profiles considered due to the variability in this parameter that involve a modest correlation coefficient ($r = -0.61$) with the slope of the muckpile

Muckpile profiles from blasts 230612, 230714 and 230419 can be rated as very flat to intermediate. Intermediate to very steep muckpile profiles, with limited displacement of the gravity center for some holes are observed in blasts 230621 and 230120, while muckpile profiles of blast 230518 vary in a wide range from flat to steep. These results are an indication of the variability in the muckpile layout between blasts and also within the same blast due mainly to a lack of control of the confinement of the holes associated to the marking procedure of the holes followed by the quarry, in which the position of the holes was defined in situ with a measuring tape by the drill rig operator according to the nominal drilling used in the quarry, i.e., burden in the range of 5.5 m and spacing between holes of 7 m.

Figure 53 Representative 2D profiles of the block (green; face green dots) and measured muckpile (red; face red dots) and their respective GCs (circles in green and red, respectively) of five categories of the slope of the muckpile. Blue line is the line that fits the front part of the muckpile profile to obtain the slope of the muckpile profile; cyan solid marker is the lowest point of the top part of the muckpile and blue solid marker is the highest point of the muckpile.

Muckpile sections rated as steep to very steep (see profiles marked with orange and red circles in the bottom right corner of the graphs in Figure 53) involve in general that limited fragments are thrown to form the pile, resulting in a steep section in the top-central part of the muckpile height (see Figure 54, left). Figure 54 also shows for comparison the layout for blast 230714 in which most of material in the front part of the muckpile is formed by fragmented rocks. To further investigate this, the ratio between the area of the Region of Interest (ROI) (i.e., area of the muckpile with fragmented rock) considered for fragmentation analysis to the block area (i.e., product between number of holes, average burden and average spacing between holes) reported in Table 6 of Deliverable D2.5 is plotted versus the slope of the muckpile, κ in Figure 55. Although the scatter in the data is high, the ratio of the area occupied by rock fragments to the initial block decreases as expected with a power function as the muckpile slope increases.

Figure 54 Muckpile layouts from blasts 230120 (left) and 230714 (right).

Figure 55 Ratio of fragmented part of the pile to the block area (see Table 6 of Deliverable D2.5) vs. the muckpile slope

3.1.3.2 Prediction of muckpile properties

Nonlinear least squares scheme using a genetic algorithm to prevent a local solution is employed to fit the horizontal displacement of the gravity center of each section before and after the blast (dx). Eq. 9 (see Table 12) describes the displacement dx as function of the variation of the rotation pressure (RPv), the effective confinement due to the first row (b_{75}), the bench height (H) and the tangent of the hole dip (D_h). The latter is a kind of fixation factor used in the Swedish theory for blast design. The positive exponent of RPv suggests that when the variability in the rotation pressure is large, which is equivalent to presence of cavities or low-quality limestone in the hole, the displacement for constant drilling parameters is smaller. Other functions of MWD parameters like the ratio CP/RPv lead to slightly smaller R^2_a (see Eq. 10, Table 12), while if the rock term is replaced by a constant term (see Eq. 11), the fitting ability decreases.

Table 12 Nonlinear regression analysis of muckpile properties: horizontal displacement of the GC of the block and muckpile (dx), final area (A_f) and slope of the muckpile.

Eq	Formula	N ^a	α	β	δ	γ	p-values ^b	R^2_a ^c	RMSE ^d
9	$dx = RPv^\alpha \cdot \exp(b_{75} \cdot \beta + H \cdot \delta) \cdot \{\gamma + \text{tg}(D_h)\}$	53	0.267	-0.164	0.141	0.303	$10^{-4}(\alpha)$ 0.149 (γ)	0.696	0.883
10	$dx = (CP/RPv)^\alpha \cdot \exp(b_{75} \cdot \beta + H \cdot \delta) \cdot \{\gamma + \text{tg}(D_h)\}$	53	0.267	-0.1764	0.150	0.996	$5.10^{-4}(\alpha)$ 0.042 (γ)	0.685	0.899
11	$dx = \exp(b_{75} \cdot \beta + H \cdot \delta) \cdot \{\gamma + \text{tg}(D_h)\}$	53	-	-0.157	0.163	0.824	$9.10^{-6}(\beta)$ 0.0695 (γ)	0.613	0.988

12	$dx/b_{75} = RPv^{\alpha} \cdot \exp(b_{75} \cdot \beta + H \cdot \delta) \cdot \{\gamma + tg(D_h)\}$	53	0.232	-0.316	0.124	0.05	$2.10^{-4}(\alpha)$ 0.628(\gamma)	0.822	0.142
13	$A_f = RPv^{\alpha} \cdot b_{75}^{\beta} \cdot \{\gamma + tg(D_h)\} \cdot A_i^{\delta}$	51	0.081	-0.268	0.967	1.49	$10^{-6}(\gamma)$ $0.002(\alpha)$	0.956	14.8
14	$\kappa = \alpha \cdot dx^{\beta}$	52	1.005	-0.517			$10^{-26}(\alpha)$ $10^{-49}(\beta)$	0.876	0.074

^aN is number of observations; ^bFor simplicity, only the two highest p-values are given and values exceeding 0.05 are typed in red; ^cR²_a: Adjusted determination coefficient; ^d RMSE: Root Mean Square Error.

The best predictions (R²_a = 0.822) are obtained with Eq. 12 (see Table 12), in which the displacement dx is normalized by the effective burden of the first row, b₇₅. Attempts have been made to include a parameter related with the explosive charging in Eq. 4 without any improvement in the prediction of the GC displacement. This effect is likely masked by the large role of the hole's confinement.

On the contrary than in Deliverable D2.5 (see Table 22), no good predictions of the swell factor are obtained in this report. As an alternative, the area of the muckpile section (A_f) is fitted with a power function of the variability of the rotation pressure (RPv), the effective burden of the first row (b₇₅), the hole inclination (D_h) and the area of the block before blasting, A_i (see Eq. 13, Table 12). For this new fit, two holes (H10 in blast 230419 and H20 in blast 230612) with atypical low and high swell factors, respectively and thus outlier final areas are removed. The resulting prediction ability is excellent, R²_a = 0.956). The studentized residuals, the absolute value of the residuals and the plot of measured versus predicted for Eq. 13 are shown in Figure 56; the fitted line has a slope of one. Note that the initial profile area is increased depending on the rock properties, and hole confinement conditions. The determination coefficient decreases to 0.948 (see Eq. 14, Table 6), when the rock term is removed from Eq. 13,

Figure 56 Results of fitting the area of muckpile sections with Eq. 6 (see Table 12): Studentized residuals for each hole (top right), distribution of absolute value of residuals (top left), and observed versus predicted of the area of muckpile sections, A_f (bottom).

Due to the good correlation (r = -0.92) between the horizontal displacement of the gravity center (dx) and the slope of the muckpile (κ), this last parameter is predicted through a power function of the GC displacement dx (see Eq. 14, Table 6); the slope of hole 10 in blast 230419 has a low atypical swell factor and it is discarded for the fit.

Eqs. 12, 13 and 14 can be used to obtain the muckpile properties (dx, A_f and κ, respectively) and later predict the trapezoidal profiles fitting the muckpile profiles (see section 7.1.12 of Deliverable D2.5).

3.1.4 Effect of blasting in digging and loading

To evaluate the downstream effect of blasting on the digging stage, the Caterpillar 390 FL that is generally employed to muck the fragments from blasting is considered; this excavator identified as Ex 451 has a bucket of 4.6 m³. The diesel refilled per day and the loading time of the trucks are considered as digging and loading KPIs.

3.1.4.1 Calculation of digging & loading KPIs

The loading time is monitored by the Truck Tracking System-TTS when a set of conditions, like truck at rest, truck adjacent to the excavator, and when the bucket is loading material, are met. This parameter accounts only for the time spend to load each truck from the loading-hauling positions within the geofences defined in the TTS, while other operations done in the absence of trucks in the vicinity of the excavator are leaving aside.

To calculate the excavator's KPIs for each blast, the days assigned to the blast from the TTS are employed (see section 6.1.1 in Deliverable D2.5). The same script used to link truck loading-hauling cycles to each blast is used to obtain the time $t_{L Bi-j}^*$ spend by the excavator Ex451 to load the trucks from each source Bi in the j^{th} day; these times are shown in Table 13 for the period in which the muckpile from blast 230222 is loaded.

Table 13 Example of calculation of digging KPIs for blast 230213.

Day ^a	Source id.	Loading time (s)			Diesel (L)	
		Correction factor, CF_j ($\beta=0.9$)	$t_{L Bi,j}^*$ for each source	$t_{L Bi,j}^* \cdot CF_j$ for blast 230213	Total consumed	Assigned to B230213
13/02/2023	230213	1.43	1308	1868	600	154
	Acopio		3785		-	-
14/02/2023	230213	1.10	14484	15930	600	600
15/02/2023	230213	1.04	15611	16313	600	600
16/02/2023	230213	1.08	12256	13228	900	900
20/02/2023	230213	1.06	12856	13615	630	630
21/02/2023	230213	1.03	16693	17179	650	650
22/02/2023	230213	1.07	10827	11595	500	447
	230222		1290		-	-
B230213		-		89727		3981

^aDays in which material from more than one source is loaded are typed in red.

Due to the errors observed in the number of trips recorded by the TTS (see Section 6.1.2 in Deliverable D2.5), these times are corrected to calculate the total loading time of the trucks that haul material from each blast:

$$t_{L Bi} = \sum_{j=1}^N t_{L Bi,j}^* \cdot CF_j \quad (15)$$

where N is the number of days spend to load the blast; and CF_j is the factor that corrects the trips monitored by the TTS based on the mass of material hauled to the plant from every position (known or unknown) and the masses monitored in the plant:

$$CF_j = \left(m_{PL,j} / m_{All-PL,j}^* \right)^\beta \quad (16)$$

The exponent $\beta = 0.9$ that provided the best reconciliation between the corrected mass hauled by the trucks is used in Eq. 19. Both CF_j and the corrected loading times for the days assigned to blast 230222 are shown in Table 13.

The volume of diesel refilled each day is provided by CEMEX. It is assumed that the diesel consumed by the excavator is equal to the fuel refilled the former day when no blending occurs in a particular day (i.e., the excavator works all the shift in the muckpile of interest), which occurs in 180 out of 200 days. But if more than one pile is loaded on the same day, the volume of diesel is distributed proportionally to the loading times spend in each source; for the example in Table 13, these

weights are 0.26 for 13 of February and 0.89 for 22 February respectively. The statistics for the resulting loading time and consumed diesel per blast are shown in Table 14. They are in the range 4 - 36 h and 1274 - 6675 L with a variability, as described by the standard deviation, of approximately 0.35 times the mean values (21 h and 3535 L).

Table 14 Digging KPIs for excavator Ex 451 and rock and blasting parameters for the 23 blasts monitored

	Loading & hauling			Rock and drilling			
	Days with blending (%)	Loading time per truck, t (h)	Diesel consumption, V_D (L)	Median burden all holes ^a , B (m)	Median burden first row ^a , B_{R1} (m)	Block volume ^b , V_r (m ³)	Feed Pressure, FP(bar)
Mean	11	20.66	3534.6	4.92	5.82	10422	75.7
Std	9	7.67	1187.6	0.32	0.98	3020	7.2

^a The burden is calculated from the profiles obtained along the direction perpendicular to the highwall face; ^b Volume between the last row and the highwall face of the blast, including the lateral highwall face (this was defined as volume V5 in Section 2.3 of Deliverable D2.3).

3.1.4.2 Prediction of digging and loading KPIs

Figure 57 shows the diesel consumption versus the loading time of the trucks in each blast; the data is differentiated by their location in the quarry to see whether this has any effect on the digging and loading performance. Additionally, for the six blasts studied in Section 3.1.3, the mean and standard deviation of the slope of the muckpile profiles and the swell factor are given; this information is completed with the respective slope categories defined in Figure 53 (see coloured circles; the mean slope of the profiles of the blast is typed in the colour of the respective slope category).

As expected, the diesel spent by the excavator per blast (in kilolitre, kL) increases as the loading time of the trucks loading time does. If a linear function of the loading time of the trucks (in h) in each blast (see Eq. 17, Table 15), the constant term $\alpha = 1.025$ kL represents the mean volume of diesel spent in other operations than digging the pile to load the trucks; it has, however, a large uncertainty due to its large p-value.

A slightly higher adjusted determination coefficient is obtained using the power function shown in Figure 57 (see Eq. 18, Table 15). The fact that the fitting ability continues to be low, indicates that other excavator activities different than loading the trucks have a large influence on the diesel spend by the excavator. This prevents better predictions when a function of the rock and blasting features is considered.

Table 15. Regression analysis to predict the volume of diesel consumed by the excavator (V_D) and the loading time of the trucks (t_L).

Eq	Formula	N^a	α	β	p-values	R^2_a	RMSE
17	$V_D = \alpha + t_L \cdot \beta$	25	1.025	0.121	$10^{-6} (\beta)$ 0.0288 (α)	0.599	0.752 kL
18	$V_D = \alpha \cdot t_L^\beta$	25	0.456	0.681	$2 \cdot 10^{-5} (\beta)$ 0.0189 (α)	0.605	0.746 kL
19	$t_L = FP \cdot V_R^\alpha \cdot F(B_{R1}/B);$ $F = \exp\{\beta \cdot (B_{R1}/B - 1)\}$	25	0.596	0.506	$2 \cdot 10^{-30} (\alpha)$ 0.0094 (β)	0.672	4.4 h
		24	0.592	0.597	$5 \cdot 10^{-30} (\alpha)$ 0.0011 (β)	0.748	3.79 h
20	$t_L/B = FP \cdot A_B^\alpha \cdot F(B_{R1}/B);$ $A_B = (N_h - N_{row}) \cdot S \cdot H$ $F(B_{R1}/B) = \exp\{\beta \cdot (B_{R1}/B - 1)\}$	25	0.520	0.680	$6 \cdot 10^{-26} (\alpha)$ 0.0013 (β)	0.649	0.996 h/m
		24	0.513	0.781	$1 \cdot 10^{-25} (\alpha)$ $9 \cdot 10^{-5} (\beta)$	0.733	0.850 h/m

^aN is number of observations.

Figure 57 Diesel consumption fitted with a power function of the loading time of the trucks; information of the muckpile slope and swell for the blasts investigated in Section 3.1.3

To predict the loading time, Eq. 19 is employed (see Table 15). In this formula, the effect of rock conditions is described with the feed pressure of the drill rig (FP, in mbar), while the volume of the rock excavated (V_r) accounts for the size of the blast. To model the heave of the blast, the function F is employed to amplify the loading time when the median drilling burden of the first row (B_{R1}) is greater than the median drilling burden of all the holes (B), which occurs in 86 % of the blasts. The statistics of the rock volume and drilling burdens (B_{R1} and B) are shown in Table 14.

Eq. 20 does not include implicitly for the burden of all the holes (B), so caution is required to apply it for blasts with a burden outside the range of the blast monitored, 4.12-5.5 m. In order to overcome this limitation, the loading time normalised by the burden is fitted with Eq. 20, in which the size of the blast is defined from the number of holes, number of rows, hole's spacing and bench height. This function has, however, a slightly worst prediction ability using either all the data or removing the outlier loading time from blast 230714 with a large residual.

3.1.5 Effect of blasting on the plant performance

Operations within the mining value chain are interdependent, and the outcomes of upstream mining activities significantly influence the efficiency of downstream processes. In this scenario, this section examines the influence of the performance of 23 blasts on ore processing at Valdilecha quarry.

Plant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) during the processing of muckpile from the blasts were linked with the lithological and mechanical characteristics of the rock mass, as well as the blast fragmentation size distribution. The Spearman correlation coefficient, ranging from -1 to 1 , is commonly used to assess the relationship between two variables. The correlation matrix of Figure 58 measures the extent to which information about one variable can be inferred by observing the other.

Figure 58 Spearman correlation plot between plant, rock lithology, MWD and fragmentation properties for 23 blasts

There are no strong relationships between the plant parameters and lithology, MWD, or fragmentation according to Figure 58. However, there is a relevant one between material transport on conveyor CC8 and fragmentation percentile sizes ($r_s=0.6$ for x_{90} and x_{85}), underscoring a reliable connection between these variables within the overall process. Percentile sizes, which define the size distribution of blast fragmentation outcomes, directly impact the amount of material passing through CC8. That indicates that when percentile sizes are bigger, a greater volume of material is transported via CC8. This actually occurs because coarser material, corresponding to larger percentile sizes, is obtained at the grizzly before undergoing comminution and further classification at the CR2 screen. As a result, a larger quantity of material moves through the associated conveyors, including CC8.

In order to establish a baseline understanding of material handling and the plant's response to the ROM, an in-depth analysis was conducted to develop a predictive model for plant rejection. The fraction of rejected material can represent 16%-42% of the material fed into the plant and is directly related to the operation of the CDD screen. The relationship between the CDD screen's operation and reject material is modelled as a linear relationship in Figure 59, predicting rejects of 35%-41% when the screen is inactive (95% confidence interval extremes for the y-intercept). Both the slope and y-intercept of this relationship are statistically significant ($p\text{-value}<0.05$).

Figure 59 Reject and CDD direct relationship

In order to develop a predictive model, three factors affecting reject were determined, two of which directly depend on the operability of the CDD screen (see Figure 60).

Figure 60 Main factors that affect the mineral recovery in the plant

3.1.5.1 Seasonality

During the wetter seasons, the amount of recovered material experiences a notable decrease. This reduction is primarily attributed to the inoperability of the CDD screen, which is adversely affected by excess moisture. To model this seasonality factor, a sinusoidal periodic function has been employed.

$$tcdd = 3,12 + 2,98 \cdot \cos (0.011 \cdot Month + 1.35) \quad (21)$$

This mathematical function¹⁰ is particularly suitable for representing the cyclical variation in the operating of the screen throughout the two years of the blasting campaigns (2023-2024). The fitting to the average operating hours of the screen per month has proven satisfactory ($R^2=0.78$) and parameters statistical significance (p -values <0.05) providing a robust predictive model.

¹⁰ This expression has been obtained in MATLAB by converting months to serial numbers using the `datetime` routine

Figure 61 Fitting of the operational working time (h) of the CDD screen by month

Boxplots in Figure 62 represent the rejection fraction and the operating of the CDD screen for each blasting campaign. During the early months of 2023, corresponding to the processing of material from the first campaign's blasts, conditions allowed the CDD screen to operate effectively. On the other hand, in 2024, in January, February and March, the screen was deactivated, which prevented the maximization of material recovery.

Figure 62 Left: Boxplots of the two blasting campaigns versus the rejection fraction. Right: Boxplots of the two blasting campaigns versus the CDD working time

3.1.5.2 Fragmentation

ROM fragment sizes significantly influence the reject fraction. All reject comes from the bypass stream, meaning it's not a subproduct of the limestone crushing process. Instead, it results directly from the screening and classification of intact blast-induced fragmentation down to the finer sizes (<40 mm). Consequently, a blast yielding a higher proportion of fines will result in a greater quantity of reject.

The proportion of fines produced by the blast is quantified as a ratio between two clear separated percentiles within the particle size distribution. This dimensionless parameter ranges from 0 to 1. A higher value indicates a steeper slope in the

size distribution curve, signifying less fines present. In Figure 63, 230213 is the blast that produces the less fines, so the ratio of low to high percentiles will be higher compared to the 230213 blast.

Figure 63 Size distribution from 230213 (blue) and 240625 (orange) blasts

3.1.5.3 Lithology

This factor, deeply intertwined with the CDD screen's operational working time, exerts also a significant influence over the rejection. Notably, when the ROM visually presents a clay-like appearance, the CDD screen is deactivated, leading to the direct channeling of all material from the bypass stream into the reject pile. Clay characterization from blasting results is performed using MWD pressure parameters. Specifically, a dimensionless ratio is calculated, comparing an MWD pressure parameter to its local variations.

3.1.5.4 Prediction formulae

A nonlinear least squares fitting is employed. The fraction of reject is modeled using the expressions presented in Table 16, which incorporate lithology, blast fragmentation, and seasonality factors. For simplicity, the results are presented by defining the factors that explain fragmentation and lithology as follows

$$MWD = \frac{CP^2}{CP_{var}} \quad (22)$$

$$x = \frac{x_{55}}{x_{85}} \quad (23)$$

These expressions consistently yield the best fits. In the first two expressions (Eq.22 and Eq.23), $S \cdot MWD \cdot x$ represents a rock quality indicator (material fed in a dry season, with less clay, and fewer fines). The exponents are negative values so the fitting suggests that lower rock quality should result in higher reject fractions as expected. However, these exponents are not statistically significant (p-values>0.05). In Eq.23, the S factor acts as a penalty term, meaning that regardless of the clay content and fragmentation occurring, the reject fraction is maximized if it is a wet season. Ultimately, the logarithmic expressions, particularly eq 4, demonstrate the best performance, with all parameters achieving statistical significance. Nevertheless, the coefficient of determination (R^2) remains below 0.5 in all cases

Table 16 Nonlinear regression analysis of reject. S (seasonality factor) MWD (lithology factor) and x (fragmentation factor)

Eq	Formula	α	β	γ	δ	ϵ	p-values ^b	R ²	RMSE
24	$R = S^\alpha \cdot MWD^\beta \cdot x^\gamma$	-0.05	-0.24	-0.24	-	-	0.29 (δ)	0.32	0.06
25	$R = \delta \cdot S^\alpha \cdot MWD^\beta \cdot x^\gamma$	-0.09	-0.11	-0.45	0.4	-	0.09 (β)	0.49	0.05
26	$R = S^\alpha \cdot e^{(\beta \cdot MWD + \gamma \cdot x^\gamma)}$	-0.11	4.6 e-4	-2.47	-	-	0.02 (β)	0.37	0.06
27	$R = \delta \cdot \log(S \cdot MWD \cdot x) + \epsilon$	-	-	-	-0.03	0.47	10 ⁻⁴ (δ)	0.43	0.05
28	$R = \delta \cdot \log(S^\alpha \cdot MWD^\beta \cdot x^\gamma) + \epsilon$	4.12	4.3	18	-7.56.10 ⁻³	0.39	0.16 (β)	0.49	0.05

In Figure 64, the rejection fraction is plotted as a function of $S \cdot MWD \cdot x$. Note how the logarithmic function intersects the points with low values of $S \cdot MWD \cdot x$, where the slope is steep until it stabilizes at a low rejection of approximately 25%. This means that for blasts with very high $S \cdot MWD \cdot x$, indicating good quality for material processing, the differences in rejection become less pronounced compared to those with low values of $S \cdot MWD \cdot x$ where the model reject prediction is more sensitive to any variation. As can be observed, the blasts in the SE and NW pits are the ones that show the highest rejection

Figure 64 Reject prediction with Eq.27.

3.2 Recommendations

3.2.1 Blast design: Working procedure for blast design to improve downstream KPIs

The use of drones or other tools, like 2D laser profilers, to survey the block before the blast is recommended to ensure:

- I. Homogenous burden in all the rows, i.e. the burden of the holes of the first row matches the nominal one.
- II. Accurate knowledge of the drilling pattern and of the volume of rock excavated, both are relevant parameters to predict fragmentation and the muckpile geometry.
- III. Uniform muckpile properties (including fragmentation) across the blast avoiding zones with limited displacement, where the loading time of the trucks (and thus the diesel consumption) is higher.

The following working procedure is ideally recommended:

- I. Survey of the block by UAV flights or other tools like 2D laser profilers and generate 3D model and a drill plan.
- II. From the rock mass characteristics obtained with the advanced rock mass characterization techniques, generate a model of the rock mass to define the charging design.
- III. Customize the charging of each borehole using a variable density explosive and appropriate decking plugs. Specific adjustments should be defined according to the geometrical conditions such as burden and real distance to the free face, and the presence of discontinuities and/or clay patches (see section 3.2.2).
- IV. Predict fragmentation, measure muckpile from UAV flights, compare and calibrate the models for a model deployment period.
- V. Correlate with downstream parameters from the digging, and plant KPIS for continuous improvements in the process.

3.2.2 Charging recommendation: Explosive decking strategy from MWD models

Blastability assessment has been conducted for the blasts in the second campaign based on the rock lithology and structure identification using the ML MWD-based model. The objective is to include the identified geological and mechanical characteristics of rocks in the blasting design for each bench.

From the lithological classes identified only the clay represent a relevant issue in blasting design, as this rock condition typically requires minimal explosive energy for fragmentation. In the present case, the explosive densities vary in the ranges of RIOFLEX Lower Density- LD ($0.7-0.8 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and RIOFLEX Higher Density-HD ($0.9-1.0 \text{ g/cm}^3$) (see Figure 65).

Figure 65 Explosive density variation indication based on lithology MWD model interpretation; HD and LD are high and low density, respectively

The strategy chosen for the presence of structures is based on the use of decks to prevent the excessive concentration and leakage of explosive mass through cavities and caverns (see Figure 66). Decks in blastholes were implemented through usage of gasbags. These gasbags are lowered to the desired depth within the blast hole and then inflated, forming a seal as depicted in Figure 67.

Figure 66 Deck position recommendation based on structural MWD model interpretation.

Figure 67 Gasbag operation procedure. 1. Lowering of the gasbag 2. Gasbag inflation

Gasbags’ length was about 30 cm. Depending on their placement, either stemming or additional explosives are loaded on top of the inflated bag. These decking devices are chosen for their ease of implementation, cost-effectiveness, and the minimal time required to install them in production holes. This requires, however, using additional booster and detonator to initiate the explosive on top of the gasbag.

For an affordable charging recommendation based in the loading capacity of the explosive –meaning the minimum depth to provide a real change of density between different rock zones–, 50 cm intervals are used as classification resolution from MWD models. Table 17 provides a summary of the operational chargeability criterion based on the detected rock characteristics of each borehole. For limestone no differentiation between lithologies is made (MLIM, DLIM, BLIM).

Table 17 Operational criteria for blasting design.

Blasthole feature	Design
Stemming	Stemming
Limestone	RIOFLEX HD
Structures	Deck (Gasbag)
Clay	RIOFLEX LD

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 - D2.2 Adaptive blast design and novel explosives, blasting products & systems.
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